

RESEARCH REPORT

Strategies for agritourism development in Gauja bioregion, Latvia, for the socioeconomic valorization of local products

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This document is an independent production from the original thesis and does not carry any official academic recognition.

This work follows on from the agrarian diagnosis carried out by Chloé Cossin in 2024 on the Gauja bioregion in Latvia. It presents the results of a six-month study conducted between March and August 2025 within the Agrosursu un ekonomikas institūts (AREI), focusing on the identification of strategies for the development of agritourism in the bioregion in response to the challenges faced by local agriculture.

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Abstract

This study aims to identify strategies for the development of agritourism in the Gauja bioregion (surrounding the national park of the same name, in Latvia), in order to better valorize both economically and socially the local productions, particularly through short supply chains, in the face of the decline of typical agriculture threatened by land pressure, lack of generational renewal, dependence on imported inputs, and market difficulties. This study is an exploratory study during which 27 stakeholders of the bioregional agritourism system were interviewed through hybrid interviews. These interviews made it possible to identify an assortment of barriers and drivers that manifest at several levels: at the level of the agritourism system in general, at the level of intra-bioregional dynamics, and at the level of the local product itself. These barriers and drivers, combined with the expectations of the interviewed stakeholders, led to the proposal of 3 strategies to develop this agritourism: clearly defining the agritourism system to make it an attractive and coherent tourist destination, establishing governance to structure this system and encourage the development of initiatives, and taking into account sustainability constraints to ensure the long-term continuation of this agritourism system.

Keywords: agritourism, short supply chain, Latvia, bioregion, national park

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List of abbreviations

AREI: Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics (from Latvian *Agroresursu un ekonomikas institūts*)

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

EAFRD: European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development

EU: European Union

Ha: Hectare

H: Hour

Km: Kilometer

LAG: Local Action Group

LEADER: Links between actions for the development of the rural economy (from the French *Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale*)

LIAA: Latvian Investment and Development Agency (from Latvian *Latvijas Investīciju un attīstības aģentūra*)

LLKC : Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre (from Latvian *Latvijas Lauku konsultāciju un izglītības centrs*)

NGO: Nongovernmental Organization

REKO: Fair Trade (from Finnish *Reilu Kuluttaminen*)

USSR: Union of Soviet Socialist Republics

Introduction

In 2024, an agrarian diagnosis was conducted in the Gauja bioregion, located in the historical region of Vidzeme in eastern Latvia, around the Gauja National Park (Cossin, 2024). A bioregion, a concept popularized by Berg and Dasmann in 1977, has been defined as referring “as much to a geographical context as to a cognitive one, that is, both to a place and to the ideas developed about ways of living in that place.” The agrarian diagnosis revealed that local agriculture takes a mosaic of forms within the bioregion. It is characterized in particular by small- and medium-scale organic family farms, often equipped with on-farm processing facilities. The Gauja bioregion has been developed around this specific form of agriculture. However, due to its particular features, it faces multiple challenges. Small and medium-sized farms suffer from strong land pressure exerted by large-scale farms and forestry operations that concentrate land ownership. Moreover, these farms are affected by an aging farming population that struggles to renew itself. From an economic standpoint, their heavy reliance on imported inputs from other European countries raises questions about their resilience and economic stability, particularly in times of crisis, as observed at the beginning of the war in Ukraine.

In addition to these challenges, these farms face major market difficulties. In Latvia, 95% of the food market is controlled by only 12 non-specialized retail chains (OECD, 2024), largely due to Latvian consumer habits favoring supermarkets for food purchases (Naglis-Liepa et al., 2022). In 2023, three foreign chains accounted for 68% of the market share (Rimi 28%, Maxima 28%, Lidl 12%) (OECD, 2024). Among these foreign chains, the share of domestic products is highly variable, sometimes below 50% for certain items such as vegetables (Latvijas Lauku konsultāciju un izglītības centrs, 2021). Organic products, in particular, struggle to gain visibility: half of organic production is marketed under conventional labels (OECD, 2019), and overall organic products are, on average, twice less represented in the Latvian food market than in other European countries (Aļeksējeva, 2024). Beyond these difficulties in valorizing specific features (local, organic), the legacy of collectivization in Latvia significantly limits cooperation among local producers, weakening their bargaining power vis-à-vis these powerful chains (Cossin, 2024).

These difficulties drive changes in the agricultural landscape of the bioregion (Cossin, 2024). In some areas, typical agriculture is gradually being replaced by large-scale entrepreneurial farms and intensive forestry, both competing for land access. The consequences are manifold: loss of identity and culture, declining territorial food autonomy, reduced landscape diversity, and, more broadly, decreased territorial attractiveness...

Two key bioregional objectives emerge from these challenges. First, preserving the local agricultural landscape and its specificities in the face of the ongoing shifts in land use. Second, galvanizing local agriculture in order to strengthen its resilience and territorial anchoring; namely, reinforcing “the capacity to prevent disasters and crises, as well as to anticipate, absorb shocks and adapt or recover in a timely, efficient and sustainable manner” (FAO, n.d.), and enhancing “the proactive proximity work of an organization with respect to the community [to] prevent and resolve problems, foster partnerships with local organizations and stakeholders, and act as a responsible citizen towards the community” (AFNOR, 2010).

To achieve these objectives, one pathway considered is the improved valorization of local production. For such valorization to be effective, it must simultaneously be economic (to maintain land use, increase farm resilience and stability, and create new market opportunities) and social (to enhance the attractiveness of the profession and improve its recognition). This study focuses on one of the potential means to achieve this improved socio-economic valorization: the development of agritourism, particularly as a way to establish short food supply chains in response to the specific marketing challenges faced by local products.

Before proceeding further, it is important to define the notions of agritourism and short food supply chains. For agritourism, the official definition recognized by the Latvian state is used here, complemented by forms of activities associated with agritourism identified in the literature. Thus, agritourism generally refers to staying on a farm while discovering the local culture and traditions. It can also include local cultural festivals, museums, handicraft exhibitions, cultural events, and attractions (Dembovska & Silicka, 2014). Agritourism can take different forms (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011): accommodation (farm stays, bed and breakfasts on farms, farm camping...) or activities (hosting school groups, farm golf, banquet halls, farm restaurants, butcher shops...). For short food supply chains, given that it remains a relatively recent concept in Latvia, this study adopts the European Union's general definition: a supply chain may be considered short when "the concerned foodstuffs are identified by, and traceable to, a farmer. The number of intermediaries between the farmer and the consumer must be 'minimal' or ideally none" (Kneafsey et al., 2012, in Praly et al., 2014).

Agritourism itself offers numerous economic and social benefits relevant to achieving the objectives of socio-economic valorization (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Dembovska & Silicka, 2014; Foris et al., 2020). Among others, it can provide a significant additional source of income for farmers (a diversification factor for the farm business and a marketing tool for farm products), it counters the loss of territorial identity by preserving local historical, cultural, and natural heritage and associated values, it creates direct connections between producers and consumers (social well-being), it supports rural employment, and it contributes to the preservation of the local agricultural landscape and its specificities¹. Similarly, short food supply chains also provide multiple economic and social benefits (Melece, 2014; Praly et al., 2014): job creation, better distribution of added value, renewed connections between rural and urban areas, revaluation of the farming profession, and improved social well-being for farmers².

¹ Other benefits of agritourism include: authentic and unique experiences for tourists, advantages for other economic sectors (transport, services, etc.), the facilitation of a balance between economic interests and the ecological framework, as well as support for local territorial development.

² Other benefits of short supply chains include: better preservation of natural resources, a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, and improved control of the food supply chain by local stakeholders.

Within this study, the relationship between the development of agritourism and the establishment of short food supply chains is grounded in three hypotheses drawn from the literature:

▫ First, the development of agritourism, through the accommodation and activities it entails, encourages on-farm sales for farms engaged in agritourism in rural and remote areas (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Horvath et al., 2023).

▫ Second, the development of agritourism crystallizes a basket of territorially embedded goods and services, thereby fostering the sale of local products through other tourism actors thanks to the positive externalities generated (Mollard & Pecqueur, 2007; Dembovska & Silicka, 2014; Foris et al., 2020).

▫ Third, the development of agritourism promotes the emergence of a territorial identity and the mobilization of territorial resources (Mollard & Pecqueur, 2007; Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Dembovska & Silicka, 2014). It thus contributes to creating a favorable territorial atmosphere for the development of short food supply chains for the marketing of local products, whether through direct farm sales or via other tourism actors, allowing local producers to take full advantage of this mode of commercialization (Corade et al., 2019; Horvath et al., 2023; Aubert & Enjolras, 2024).

Accordingly, this study seeks to answer the following question: from a perspective of preserving and galvanizing the bioregional agricultural landscape and its specificities, what strategies can be implemented to develop agritourism in order to promote short supply chains and thus enhance the economic and social value of local productions?

To address this question, a three-step approach was adopted. First, an exploratory study based on the local and national context was conducted to gather qualitative data from stakeholders in the bioregional agritourism system on potential barriers and drivers for development. Second, the results were analyzed to reveal the nature of these barriers and drivers, as well as their expression at the territorial scale. Finally, these barriers and drivers were mobilized and connected with stakeholders' expectations in order to propose three major development strategies aimed at overcoming the barriers and capitalizing on the drivers.

I. The bioregional agritourism system as a novel object of study in Latvia

Agritourism in the Gauja bioregion represents an unprecedented object of study. To address it properly, it is essential to understand the surrounding context, both in terms of tourism and agriculture, in order to develop an appropriate methodology for collecting relevant data to answer this study's research question, as well as to identify the right stakeholders from whom to obtain such data.

I.1. A tourism situation shaped by dynamics at multiple scales

In Latvia, tourism is expressed through dynamics that vary according to the scale considered. To understand the tourism situation within the bioregion, it is necessary to examine these dynamics at each of these levels.

I.1.a. Tourism in Latvia largely dominated by Riga

Latvia is divided into five administrative regions ([Figure 1](#)): Riga, Vidzeme, Zemgale, Kurzeme, and Latgale. Each of these regions is subdivided into several municipalities with their own administrations, and each municipality is further divided into several parishes.

Figure 1 – Map of Latvia's planning regions after the 2021 reform (Wikipedia contributors, 2025)

Tourism in Latvia has been booming in recent years, recording one of the strongest growth rates at the European level (Lukjanova, 2019). Between 2021 and 2023, the number of tourists rose from 1,306,588 to 2,435,795 (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024b), with a peak season from May to September. Domestic tourism accounted for 43.0% of the tourist flow in 2023, followed by Lithuanians (10.6%), Estonians (7.5%), Germans (5.3%), Finns (4.3%), British (3.6%), and Poles (2.5%).

Tourism in Latvia is defined by the 1998 Tourism Law as well as EU directives and international tourism standards since 2002 (Kaufmane, 2011). This law organizes the tourism industry to achieve several strategic objectives: sustainable tourism development,

decentralization, hospitality, the creation and preservation of an attractive and distinctive tourism image, cooperation and individual initiatives, modernization, mobility and accessibility, professionalism, and safety. Latvian tourism policy is framed as an international economic policy, particularly oriented towards European countries through several EU legislative projects: “A renewed EU tourism policy: Towards a stronger partnership for European tourism” (2006), “Agenda for a sustainable and competitive European tourism” (2007), and “Correlation between the labor market and regional needs in the tourism sector” (2009).

To date, tourism in Latvia is largely dominated by Riga, the capital (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024b). Of the 2,435,795 tourists in 2023, 71.8% visited Riga and its surrounding area (Pierīga), more than the total number of tourists in 2021. This monopoly of attractiveness is explained by several issues affecting the development of tourism in the four other regions (Lukjanova, 2019). Reported issues include: geographically uneven distribution of tourism supply, limited funding and development opportunities, insufficient support and cooperation with local authorities, lack of originality and communication regarding tourism offers, weak regional positioning, and underdeveloped transport infrastructure.

The Gauja bioregion, located in Vidzeme, extends mainly within this region and partly into Riga. Vidzeme is the third most visited Latvian region, attracting 6.9% of total tourist flows and 2.6% of international visitors (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024b). Two-thirds of these tourists are day-trippers. Tourism in this region is closely tied to the Gauja National Park.

I.1.b. Gauja national park, a major domestic tourism destination at the heart of environmental concerns

The Gauja national park is one of Latvia’s most significant tourist destinations. Located in the northeast of the Vidzeme region (Figure 2), it is the country’s oldest and largest national park (Šteinfelde, 2020). The park covers 91,750 hectares and is crossed by the Gauja River over 95 kilometers (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment,” 2023). Administratively, it is divided among four municipalities: Cēsis (68.8%), Sigulda (20.1%), Valmiera (11.1%), and Saulkrasti (0.1%). Today, land ownership is predominantly private: 67% of the land is privately owned, 29% belongs to the state, and 4% to municipalities.

Figure 2 – Map showing the location of Gauja national park in Latvia (Taff, 2007)

The park is renowned for its natural and cultural features. It has a diversified landscape composed of river valleys and ravines, large forested areas, and agricultural land. Urban areas account for only a small share of the land distribution: 57% consists of forests (deciduous, coniferous, mixed), 35% of agricultural land, 3% of water bodies (rivers, lakes), 2% of wetlands, and 2% of built-up areas (Figure 3). These features make the park an ecologically significant area (Livine & Reddy, 2017), home to rich biodiversity³, with numerous caves, cliffs, and rock formations providing valuable ecological niches. The park also harbors important cultural and historical heritage, including castles, manors, urban monuments, and archaeological sites.

Unlike other natural parks, the Gauja National Park was not established primarily for its fauna but rather for its natural and cultural landscape. It is a landmark of Latvian history whose heritage significance is recognized both nationally and at the European level. This concept of the park as a complete landscape forms the backbone of its identity.

(Legend translation: artificial areas: urban, industrial, and commercial infrastructure, urban green spaces; agricultural areas: cultivated land, plantations, pastures, complex cropping systems; forests and natural areas: deciduous, coniferous, mixed forests, other wooded land; wetlands: peat bogs; water bodies: rivers, lakes, and other water surfaces)

Figure 3 – Map of land use in Gauja national park (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment.” 2023)

³ There are 170 bird species and 52 mammal species (including 10 protected ones) in Gauja national park.

The park attracts about 1 million visitors annually (Šteinfelde, 2020), mostly domestic tourists, with a notable presence of Lithuanian and Estonian visitors. These tourists are primarily drawn to the park’s “pristine” landscape and can enjoy a wide and diversified range of services: accommodation, restaurants, leisure activities, etc. (Livine & Reddy, 2017). The majority are day-trippers, with only a small share staying for several days. The park saw renewed interest during the Covid-19 crisis, when a nationwide trend toward revitalizing local tourism emerged in Latvia (Šteinfelde, 2020). However, while domestic tourism increased, the closure of borders with Russia and Belarus negatively affected international arrivals (though precise statistics are lacking).

The 2023–2035 Conservation Plan for Gauja National Park aims to integrate ecological, aesthetic, and cultural criteria into municipal planning, with the objectives of preserving biodiversity, protecting historical heritage, and improving the management of open and forested areas (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment”, 2023). In this regard, the development of sustainable tourism plays a key role in meeting these objectives, raising questions about the balance between conservation and public accessibility. Several management zones exist within the park (Figure 4). Apart from strictly protected areas, where access is prohibited, restrictions mainly concern construction and the organization of activities (in terms of group size). Importantly, there are no restrictions on agricultural activities. Nevertheless, agriculture plays a vital role in the park: it contributes to maintaining its landscape by preserving open areas that support biodiversity, and through its diversity, strengthens the complexity and attractiveness of this landscape. For this reason, local agriculture was one of the key drivers behind the creation of the Gauja bioregion, which was initially conceived in relation to this natural park.

3.1. attēls. Teritorijas, kuras ierosināts iekļaut GNP teritorijā, lai nodrošinātu dabas vērtību aizsardzību

(Legend translation: red = strict regulation zone; khaki = nature reserve; yellow = landscape protection zone; purple = cultural and historical heritage zone; gray = neutral zone; dark green = five areas proposed for integration into the national park)

Figure 4 – Map of the different management zones within Gauja national park (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment,” 2023)

I.1.c. The Gauja bioregion, a participatory initiative with agriculture at its core

The bioregion is a recent project that was formalized in 2023 with the signing of a memorandum by 13 organizations (Ozola, 2025). Among these organizations, four were the municipalities sharing part of the national park: Cēsis, Sigulda, Valmiera, and Saulkrasti. The bioregion is not an administrative unit but rather a region defined by geophysical (climate, geography, ecosystem) and sociocultural characteristics. It is an informal structure, neither state-run nor administrative, governed horizontally through voluntary initiatives by participating stakeholders around common objectives. Citizens play a key role in setting these objectives through monthly participatory workshops designed to gather their input. However, it should be noted that the municipality of Saulkrasti agreed to participate in the bioregion only for the portion of its territory within the park (0.1%), and is therefore not considered an active stakeholder in the initiative. By definition, the bioregion has no administrative boundaries; it is first and foremost a conceptual territory encompassing the Gauja national park and, to some extent, neighboring areas within the municipalities of Cēsis, Sigulda, and Valmiera (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Map of the territory generally considered as bioregional (Ozola, 2025)

The agrarian diagnosis conducted by Cossin in 2024 highlighted an agriculture with specificities diverging from national trends. The bioregion shows a higher share of organic farms (Table 1) compared to the national average (12.2% in 2022) (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024a). Agriculture here is highly diversified, food-oriented, and often equipped with on-farm processing facilities, while at the national level, the dominant crops are cereals

(61.2% of agricultural land), fodder crops (19.3%), and industrial crops such as rapeseed (12.1%). A duality exists between the majority of small- and medium-scale family farms and the minority of large-scale entrepreneurial farms that concentrate land ownership.

Table 1 – Data on agriculture and housing in the municipalities of the Gauja bioregion (Ozola, 2025, data from 2024)

	Cēsis Municipality	Sigulda Municipality	Valmiera Municipality	Total
Area (km ²)	2 668,13	1 029,90	2 947,92	6 645,95
Population	43 438	32 507	52 452	128 397
Population density (inhab/km ²)	16	31	18	N/A
Organic area (ha)	17 325	4 297	10 477	32 099
% of organic area	33%	17%	15%	N/A
Organic farms	207	57	125	389

The bioregion currently pursues 8 objectives, including the development of agritourism and short food supply chains. Although the Gauja National Park is a major tourism destination, farmer participation in agritourism initiatives has remained limited. No study has yet been conducted on agritourism within the bioregion, and the term “agritourism” has no direct equivalent in Latvian. Instead, it is subsumed under the broader notion of “rural tourism” (*lauku tūrisms* in Latvian), officially defined by the Republic of Latvia as a “type of tourism offering tourists the opportunity to rest or use accommodation in rural areas, drawing on local social, cultural, and natural resources.” Hence, research is needed to better understand agritourism dynamics at the territorial scale.

Beyond its intrinsic academic interest and the benefits of agritourism and short supply chains in addressing the challenges faced by local agriculture, it is important to emphasize that these two themes are embedded in multiple policies operating across different scales and involving multiple actors. At the European level, relevant frameworks include the Farm to Fork Strategy of the Green Deal (Aļeksējeva, 2024), as well as the LEADER initiative of the EAFRD program (Melece, 2014), which Latvia joined in 2006 (European CAP Network, 2023) and which funds several Local Action Groups (LAGs) in the bioregion. At the national level, they are incorporated into Latvia’s Rural Development Programme (OECD, 2019). At the regional level, strategies exist within Vidzeme for promoting a sustainable food system (Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2023). Finally, at the local level, they align with policies such as the 2023–2035 Gauja National Park Action Plan (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment,” 2023) and the Tourism Action Plan led by sector professionals. Thus, beyond a mere research interest, there is a concrete practical utility in conducting a study specifically on this theme.

I.2. An exploratory study conducted with actors of the bioregional agritourism system to identify barriers and drivers for the development of agritourism

In a context where agritourism has not yet been studied in the bioregion, the currently available and accessible data are very limited, which makes quantitative approaches (based on economic, financial, or market data) difficult to implement. An exploratory study was therefore necessary in order to obtain preliminary insights that could serve as a basis for developing strategies grounded in the identification of existing barriers and levers.

I.2.a. Interviews to obtain qualitative data on six themes related to the development of agritourism

To identify strategies for the development of agritourism in the bioregion, it was first necessary to determine the fundamental elements that play a role in the emergence and effective functioning of an agritourism system. To this end, several studies on agritourism development (carried out in different European countries) were analyzed to extract the barriers and drivers identified by the authors. These were complemented by studies on the development of rural tourism in Latvia, in order to better account for local specificities, and by studies on the development of short food supply chains, to better understand how they can be integrated into an agritourism system.

From this review, barriers and drivers were grouped into six conditions influencing the development of agritourism: territorial identity, socio-economic context, state of knowledge, need for training, infrastructures, and inter-actor cooperation.

The development of agritourism requires the identification and promotion of a territorial identity that contributes both to the attractiveness of the agritourism offer (Mollard & Pecqueur, 2007; Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Boigey et al., 2024) and to the development of short food supply chains (Bavel et al., 2018). It requires taking into account the local socio-economic context and the related challenges (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Kurtyka-Marcak & Janowska-Biernat, 2020; Boigey et al., 2024). It requires that the concept of agritourism and its specificities be well understood by the different actors of the agritourism system (Dembovska & Silicka, 2014; Boigey et al., 2024), as well as an understanding of consumer (i.e. tourist) demand for local products (Corade et al., 2022). It requires farmers to mobilize new skills beyond those related to agricultural production (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Kurtyka-Marcak & Janowska-Biernat, 2020; Boigey et al., 2024). It requires adequate infrastructures, both at the farm and territorial levels, to contribute to accessibility, hospitality, and the overall attractiveness of the tourist destination and its offer (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Kurtyka-Marcak & Janowska-Biernat, 2020; Boigey et al., 2024). Finally, it requires effective cooperation among all actors in the agritourism system (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Kaufmane, 2011; Boigey et al., 2024), particularly in setting up short food supply chains (Bavec et al., 2018; Corade et al., 2022).

To assess the state of these six conditions in the bioregion, hybrid interviews (with both structured and semi-structured questions) were conducted to collect qualitative data on each of them. An interview guide was developed, treating each condition as a discussion theme.

For each of the six themes, several questions were designed based on the barriers, drivers, and contextual elements identified in the literature. The interview guide was translated into English and Latvian for practical use. The English version is available in [Appendix 1](#). With the information sought and the methodology established, the next step was to determine the actors from whom such information could be collected.

I.2.b. Interviews with four categories of actors identified as key components of the Latvian agritourism system

At present, there is no official definition of the actors involved in the Latvian agritourism system. However, the Latvian rural tourism system was studied by Kaufmane (2011), who identified four subsystems. For this study, these four subsystems were used as a basis for proposing four key categories of actors involved in agritourism in Latvia ([Figure 6](#)):

- Service providers: they offer services to agritourists and act as the economic engine of the agritourism offer. Two subcategories are considered here: farmers on the one hand, and other service providers (restaurants, hotels, shops, etc.) on the other.
- Institutions: they actively support the actors who constitute the agritourism offer.
- Promoters: they communicate and promote the agritourism offer in order to connect supply and demand.
- Attractiveness creators: by generating attractiveness, they stimulate the activity of service providers by complementing the agritourism offer.

Figure 6 – Diagram of the main actors of the Latvian agritourism system and their interactions (author, 2025, adapted from Kaufmane, 2011)

The study perimeter also had to be defined in order to identify which actors within these four categories should be targeted. This perimeter is difficult to delineate geographically since the

bioregion does not yet have fixed boundaries. However, given that the bioregion is envisioned as a territory centered around the Gauja National Park, the study area was defined as the agritourism system shaped by the actors operating within the park and its immediate surroundings.

Actors were identified through different approaches. Some were identified in the literature or through targeted internet searches for each of the four categories. Others were recommended by resource persons or by interviewees themselves. For farmers specifically, the contact list established during the bioregional agrarian diagnosis was used, given the difficulty of identifying them through other means.

I.3. A diversified corpus of actors characteristic of local specificities

The actors previously identified were contacted and interviews were conducted with them to collect data for this study.

I.3.a. A study conducted with 27 actors located in four different municipalities

A total of 93 actors were contacted during May and June 2025, with 112 follow-ups (i.e. a median of 2 follow-ups per actor), resulting in a response rate (positive and negative) of 40.8%. Contact methods included emails, SMS, and direct prospecting. This process led to 27 interviews with actors from the territory. The detailed results of the contact phase by actor category are presented in [Table 2](#).

Table 2 – Results of the contact phase (author, 2025)

Response obtained after contact	Service providers		Institutions	Promoters	Attractiveness creators	Total responses (units)	Total responses (%)
	Farmers	Other service providers					
Positive response	10	1	10	3	3	27	29,0%
Refusal	2	1	5	2	1	11	11,8%
No response/ no follow-up	24	14	5	8	4	55	59,1%
Total contacts	36	16	20	13	8	93	100,0%

Among the 27 interviews, 22 were conducted in English and 5 in Latvian. When the interview was conducted in Latvian, an interpreter was present to provide simultaneous translation. In addition, a system was specifically developed to facilitate understanding of the interviewee's statements. This system enabled real-time translation, making it easier to follow the conversation and extract verbatims. However, this system was imperfect in its translations and could not fully replace an interpreter. Its technical details are provided in [Appendix 2](#). The reliance on an interpreter, particularly for interviewing farmers, required several meetings to be rescheduled, thereby reducing the availability for other interviews.

It is also important to note that, for logistical reasons (linked to the availability of the service vehicle), 11 out of 27 interviews were conducted online. While this format facilitated the

organization of discussions, it may have affected the openness of some participants, the ability to conduct field observations, and the immersion in their working environment. Furthermore, 3 out of 27 interviews (2 institutional actors and 1 promoter) were conducted asynchronously due to these actors' limited availability. This modality may have reduced the depth of exchanges and limited the capture of relational dimensions (emotional expression, interactional dynamics).

The interviews took place across four municipalities: Cēsis, Sigulda, Valmiera, and Ogre (Figure 7). They lasted from 1h07 to 2h46, with a median duration of 1h53. Aside from occasional comprehension difficulties related to language barriers, no significant issues were encountered. Overall, the interviews went smoothly, with all sampled actors showing openness and hospitality. Complementary discussions with other researchers were also carried out during a thematic workshop and an excursion organized in the Gauja bioregion as part of the European Society for Rural Sociology Congress held in Riga in July 2025.

Figure 7 – Map of the spatial distribution of interviewed stakeholders and objects in the study area (bioregion) (author, 2025)

I.3.b. A diversified sample of actors that provided representative information, but with certain limitations

The interview sample included 27 actors: 10 farmers, 1 other service provider, 10 institutional actors, 3 promoters, and 3 attractiveness creators.

Among the 10 farmers interviewed, none were located in the municipality of Cēsis. During the contact phase, two farmers mentioned reasons for refusal that may also apply to those in this municipality: absence during the interview period and lack of labor (and therefore time to dedicate to an interview). However, the sampled farmers' characteristics in terms of location, certification, management practices, sectors of activity, marketing channels, and farm sizes reflect the specificities of the bioregional agricultural landscape as identified in the literature (Cossin, 2024). Details of the interviewed farmers are provided in [Figure 8](#).

Other service providers proved much more difficult to reach. Only one restaurant agreed to be interviewed (and cited). This was a restaurant in the village of Līgatne, awarded a Michelin Green Star, which exclusively sources organic products within a 100-kilometer radius. Several reasons could explain the low responsiveness of other establishments (lack of time, lack of interest, or limited profitability), but it is difficult to know precisely, since these actors did not provide explicit reasons despite being asked for clarification. One restaurant initially agreed but canceled due to last-minute unforeseen circumstances and did not respond to subsequent follow-ups.

Among the 10 institutional actors interviewed, 7 belonged to one of the 13 organizations that signed the bioregion memorandum: the municipalities of Sigulda, Valmiera, and Cēsis; Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences, which has research programs on tourism; the Nature Conservation Agency, a government institution in charge of environmental protection; the Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre (LLKC), which supports rural entrepreneurs; and the Institute of Agricultural Resources and Economics (AREI), a national agronomic research institute. The 3 other institutional actors belonged to the following institutions: the Vidzeme Planning Region, the LAG No Salacas līdz Rūjai, which supports local entrepreneurial projects, and the Latvian Investment and Development Agency (LIAA), attached to the Ministry of Economics, which aims to stimulate the competitiveness of Latvian businesses and attract foreign investors.

Among the 5 institutional actors who refused to participate, 4 justified their refusal by declaring themselves insufficiently qualified on the topic. It was unfortunately not possible to meet with the 3 other LAGs in the territory: one refused, considering that an interview would not provide more information than that already given by a colleague, while the other two never responded despite multiple follow-ups.

Figure 8 - Overview of the farms systems encountered during interviews

The 3 promoters interviewed were:

- Nature Center: a venue dedicated to promoting Gauja National Park and its natural heritage. Its role is to highlight the park's biodiversity and ecological niches through awareness-raising.

- EnterGauja: a cluster of businesses located in and around Gauja National Park and a signatory of the bioregion memorandum. Entrepreneurs can join to benefit from networking opportunities and digital promotion to tourists.

- Sigulda Tourism Center: tourism centers operate under the authority of their respective municipalities. They promote the municipal tourism offer and highlight it to tourists through various projects.

It is also worth noting the indirect participation (without interview) of LIAA's international promotion service, which is responsible for promoting Latvian tourism abroad and provided useful complementary insights. Two notable promoters could not be interviewed. First, no tour operators could be reached: one declined, citing being too busy and not involved in agritourism. Second, Lauku Ceļotājs, a trans-Baltic rural tourism association identified by several actors as central to agritourism development and a key interlocutor, declined without justification.

Finally, the 3 attractiveness creators interviewed were all markets:

- Mūsu Bio Tirgus: a monthly market in Sigulda with around 30 local producers (farmers, ~30% of whom are organic, and artisans), usually attracting around 500 visitors per event.

- Slow Food Straupe tirdziņš: a bi-monthly market in Straupe with around 100 local producers (10 farmers per artisan), all located within 50 kilometers and committed to ecological practices, usually attracting between 3,000 and 5,000 visitors per event.

- Novada Garša: a national digital market developed by LLKC, acting as a platform connecting local producers with consumers.

One local market declined an interview due to lack of time. It was also not possible to meet with local festivals. One responded, indicating that their contact address was inactive outside festival periods, but by then the analysis phase had already begun, making it impossible to schedule an interview.

Despite these limitations, it was possible to collect useful information from this diversified sample, which overall reflects the characteristics of the bioregional agritourism system. This allowed for the identification of barriers and drivers to agritourism development in the bioregion, which will now be presented.

II. A bioregional agritourism system with strengths whose potential is constrained by several barriers highlighted through interviews

The data collected were analyzed through cross-comparison of the responses provided by each of the 27 actors interviewed for the six themes of the interview guide. This cross-analysis aimed to reveal several insights: the main elements of response, disagreements between actors, the frequency of recurring ideas, the influence of actor categories on responses, the degree of knowledge of the interviewee on the topic, as well as the attitude and mindset expressed. This made it possible to identify a set of barriers and opportunities that appear to be structured across three levels of analysis: the overall organization of the agritourism system, intra-bioregional territorial dynamics, and the product itself.

II.1. A chaotic organization of the agritourism system that hinders its development

Study of the bioregional agritourism system shows a sector in the making, marked by structural difficulties largely explained by psychological and human-related barriers at the individual level.

II.1.a. An emerging agritourism system in search of definition

Farms whose models resemble those typical of the bioregion have been identified as more likely to develop agritourism activities in Latvia (Aļeksēja, 2024). Indeed, agritourism exists in multiple forms in the bioregion, but it is not always recognized as such by the actors interviewed. Among the 10 farmers interviewed, 8 out of 10 offered activities associated with agritourism on their farms (Table 3), yet 4 of these 8 farmers did not consider themselves as engaging in agritourism (farmers n°1, n°2, n°3, and n°7).

Table 3 – Agritourism activities organized on the farms of interviewed farmers (author, 2025)

n°	Agritourism activities offered	n°	Agritourism activities offered
1	On-farm sales, accommodation, historic building, thematic workshops, concerts, crafts, garden	5	On-farm sales (dedicated facility), professional visits, awareness workshops
2	On-farm sales, pick-your-own	6	Accommodation, historic building, school visits, banquets, concerts
3	On-farm sales, pick-your-own	7	Professional visits
4	On-farm sales (dedicated facility), tastings	8	On-farm sales, tastings, professional visits

This lack of recognition raises questions about how actors define the concept. As noted earlier, agritourism is a relatively recent notion in Latvia, still lacking clear definition: “it is only in the past few years that we have started to pay attention to it” (institutional actor). Its definition is strongly influenced by the expectations and individual projections of actors, as well as by their personal experiences. For instance, 7 out of 27 respondents reported first discovering agritourism abroad, in Italy or France. As a result, agritourism is often poorly distinguished from rural tourism, and the definitions offered tend to be partial, shaped by empiricism and the subjectivity of individual expectations. This absence of a shared definition can be identified as a major difficulty for coordination and the implementation of projects in this field.

The interviews revealed four main expectations associated with agritourism among system actors: disconnection from everyday life, a return to roots, authenticity of the experience, and personal enrichment.

Agritourists seek the opportunity to disconnect from their daily routines and escape the stress of urban life. They perceive agritourism as a form of escape, a return to nature and the “quality of life” (promoter) it offers. For them, agritourism fits within a slow tourism dynamic, where time can be taken to fully appreciate the experience. “They want to avoid mass tourism” (institutional actor), preferring calm, peaceful settings conducive to well-being. Agritourists are also motivated by a search for “roots!” (farmer) from which they have become detached after leaving their native countryside. In Latvia in particular, the countryside carries a near-patriotic dimension and constitutes one of the main foundations of Latvian identity (Aistara, 2018). Thus, many express the desire to reconnect with family traditions and know-how. They want to experience the “Latvian lifestyle” (promoter) and revive the emotional ties linking them to the countryside and to childhood memories.

Authenticity is another key expectation: agritourists seek experiences built around the farm and its products. This often intersects with gastronomic tourism, as agritourists want to explore the territory through traditional, high-quality products that contrast with their everyday consumption habits.

Finally, agritourism is valued as a means of personal enrichment. It enables visitors to develop a deeper understanding of the agricultural world: “they like to see how things are done nowadays” (farmer). Human interaction and exchanges with passionate farmers are essential, creating immersion in everyday farm life and offering opportunities to discover processes and know-how. For young children in particular, agritourism functions as both recreation and education.

According to the interviews, agritourists are mainly families with young children, attracted by the educational aspects and contact with animals, but they may also be groups of active adults (30–60 years old) or dynamic seniors. Young people, however, seem less interested in this type of tourism. Agritourists are primarily urban dwellers from Riga and its metropolitan area, though visitors also come from abroad, particularly Estonia (especially in the north, near the border), Lithuania, and to a lesser extent other European countries (Germany, Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, etc.). They typically belong to the middle or upper-middle classes, with sufficient purchasing power to buy local products. Lower-income groups lack the financial resources to engage in agritourism (economic barrier), while wealthier groups generally show little interest.

Agritourists share an emotional connection to the rural environment (through nature, culture, or heritage), with food playing a central role in their lifestyle. Most are excursionists rather

than long-stay visitors. Several factors explain this national trend toward short stays (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024b): lack of motivation (26% of cases), financial constraints (23.5%), health or mobility issues (22.2%), and lack of time (16%).

Thus, while the contours of the bioregional agritourism system are beginning to take shape, its current structuring faces significant limitations.

II.1.b. An agritourism system endowed with the fundamentals for its development but subject to strong structural atomization and a lack of specialization

To foster agritourism, several opportunities currently exist in terms of financial support, training programs, project mentoring, cooperation initiatives, and even communication strategies regarding the tourism offer.

It proved difficult, however, to clearly identify the actors toward whom stakeholders can turn today to request financial support for developing agritourism activities. Only three actors were identified with certainty. First, the LAGS (cited by 13/27 actors) provide funding for rural development projects through the LEADER program, financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). The Rural Support Service (Lauku atbalsta dienests, mentioned by only 1/27 actors) is a state body distributing funds in line with the objectives of Latvia's Rural Development Programme. These funds are co-financed by the European Union (EAFRD, CAP) and the Latvian state. The third is ALTUM (Attīstības finanšu institūcija Altum, mentioned by 1/27 actors). Contacted via email, ALTUM describes itself as a financial institution offering funding instruments aligned with national development objectives, mainly in the form of loan guarantees with preferential rates more advantageous than those of traditional banks. These loans are co-financed by the Latvian state and the EAFRD. Other funding possibilities were mentioned, such as through municipalities or the LLKC, though these organizations did not reference such funding opportunities during interviews. LIAA was also cited, but it was stressed that these funds are now obsolete, as they were restricted to actors enrolled in programs whose registration periods are now closed.

In addition, there exists a diversity of accessible training programs. Stakeholders can attend seminars or short courses providing basic knowledge of organizing tourism activities, hospitality and customer service, as well as product presentation. Several actors offer such training: EnterGauja, the Straupe SlowFood Market, the Vidzeme Planning Region, Lauku Ceļotājs, municipal tourism and business centers, LLKC, and LIAA. More advanced academic and certified training is also available through the Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences, and technical schools. Professional study trips abroad are another option. These aim to provide exposure to agritourism practices in other countries, encouraging experiential learning and peer exchange. Zemnieku Saeima (the country's largest farmers' association) organizes exchanges between Latvia and Uzbekistan; LLKC organizes study visits both within Latvia and abroad; and Lauku Ceļotājs offers trips within the Baltics, Scandinavia, and Central Asia. Finally, other programs focus more specifically on tourism business management. The Valmiera Development Agency provides training on digitalization; LIAA offers courses on both digitalization and sustainable business practices.

Regarding project mentoring and support for agritourism development, several avenues are available. LLKC consultants can respond to farmers' specific requests by seeking out the required information or referring them to a more appropriate actor. The Rural Support Service provides guidance for accessing funding. Lauku Ceļotājs offers consultations on various aspects of rural tourism (financing, marketing, project development). Farmers' associations and professional networks may also provide advice in a more informal context, as well as opportunities to share experiences related to agritourism. Farmers may also hire private experts for assistance with business management and accounting. For more comprehensive support, LIAA collaborates with municipal business centers to provide business incubators. These incubators serve as fertile environments for exchange and guidance, though they target young entrepreneurs (less than three years in operation) and do not offer agritourism-specific tools. The most effective form of support appears to come from the LAGs, which help farmers access European funding and provide professionalized follow-up throughout the project's development. They can also direct farmers to other partners for legal or accounting advice.

There are also several cooperation initiatives. Business clusters have been established by LIAA, municipalities, and EnterGauja. Strategic projects are carried out by LAGs, municipal tourism centers, or the Ministry of Agriculture, such as the national program LA 20 "Cooperation to promote the functioning of short food supply chains and ensure supply", which also applies to the tourism sector. Cooperation initiatives between local entrepreneurs (farmers, other tourism service providers, and farmers' associations) exist as well, alongside agritourism routes (rye and cider routes) developed by Lauku Ceļotājs, which operate at a broader territorial scale than the bioregion but include some members from the study area. Finally, bioregional working groups have been established, and there are intentions to integrate tourism into their future agenda.

Several channels exist for communicating about agritourism offers. Online platforms include AirBnB, where one can find guesthouses or farm stays; EnterGauja, which lists activities within and around the national park, organized by category (nature, history, festivals...); Lauku Ceļotājs, which, beyond developing agritourism routes, catalogues rural tourism activities available in Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia; and municipal websites, which present local tourism activities. Offline channels are also in place: municipal tourism centers can direct visitors to agritourism activities; information boards throughout the region list nearby attractions; local markets and actor networks also promote agritourism by word of mouth. Finally, LIAA's marketing service promotes agritourism both domestically and internationally, following a strategy structured around prioritized markets. For example, it recently contributed to an article on Latvian agritourism published in the Finnish newspaper *Maaseudun Tulevaisuus* (Lamminen, 2025).

A majority of actors interviewed believe that it is relatively easy to find information about agritourism in the bioregion (15/27). However, 12/27 disagreed, pointing to certain difficulties. They feel that agritourism is insufficiently highlighted as such (lacking differentiation from other forms of rural tourism), that there is no coordinated tourism offer at the bioregional scale (offers remain fragmented between municipalities), and that foreign visitors who do not speak Latvian may struggle to find reliable information. "The information is fragmented", "the information should be more easily accessible" (institutional actors). Furthermore, some farmers engaged in agritourism do not advertise their activities online.

Yet, these difficulties are not limited to communication opportunities: they are evident across all development opportunities. While financial support does exist, it is neither clear, nor coordinated, nor tailored specifically to agritourism (instead framed within rural development/rural tourism). As one farmer explained: “it’s not always easy to find, you don’t know where to look.” Some actors also judged available support insufficient in both duration and amount. Regarding training and mentoring opportunities, interviewees highlighted the absence of a comprehensive, specialized, long-term offer. Cooperation initiatives were described as decentralized, lacking interconnections, unstable over time, and with limited capacity to generate concrete dynamics. “Sometimes there are so many things happening that we cannot keep track of them all” (institutional actor). At present, no cooperation initiative explicitly dedicated to agritourism exists, except perhaps those proposed by Lauku Ceļotājs, which operate at a scale larger than the bioregion and are not explicitly framed under the agritourism label.

In addition, there is a striking lack of mutual awareness among actors concerning available opportunities. Indeed, 14/27 actors (including 8/10 farmers) were unable to clearly cite organizations capable of providing financial support. While most were aware of the existence of European or national funding, their understanding of the topic remained vague. Regarding training programs, 11/27 actors were uninformed or poorly informed, while in terms of mentoring opportunities, 14/27 lacked sufficient knowledge. Ten of the 27 actors (7 of them farmers) were unable to name any cooperation initiatives. Even among the better-informed, perspectives remained partial.

This glaring lack of mutual awareness results from the atomization of cooperation within the agritourism system, leading to a proliferation of uncoordinated and short-term initiatives. The main reason for this atomization lies in the lack of cooperation among farmers. Farmers are already the category least able to name relevant actors for agritourism development ([Table 4](#)), citing on average fewer than three. They are also by far the least cooperative in tourism matters: 4/10 farmers interviewed had no cooperation partners in this area, despite their central role in agritourism development ([Table 5](#)). Moreover, when cooperation does exist, it usually remains at the local scale and involves only a limited number of actors. This leads to the emergence of multiple microcosms that hinder the establishment of collective initiatives around agritourism.

Table 4 – Average number of actors cited for agritourism development by category of actor, based on interview responses (author, 2025)

Actor category	Farmers	Other service providers	Institutional actors	Promoters	Attractiveness creator
Number of respondents	10	1	10	3	3
Average number of actors cited	2,9	3	5,9	4	4

Table 5 – Types of partners in tourism matters by category of actor, based on partners cited during interviews (author, 2025)

Actor/Partner	Farmers	Other service providers	Institutions	Promoters	Attractiveness creator	No partner
Farmers (/10)	2	3	4	2	2	4
Other service providers (/1)	0	1	1	0	0	0
Institutional actors (/10)	7	8	9	6	4	1
Promoters (/3)	2	2	3	1	2	0
Attractiveness creator (/3)	3	3	2	1	2	0
Total (/27)	14	17	19	10	10	5

II.1.c. Microcosms explained by psychological and human barriers that constrain individuals' ability to cooperate

These microcosms, which result from farmers' lack of cooperation around tourism-related issues, can be explained by psychological (mental, emotional) and human (organizational, social, cultural) barriers.

Engaging in agritourism requires skills beyond those associated with production activities. The interviews revealed that seven human and commercial skills must be mastered by farmers to develop such activities:

- the ability to design an agritourism product that includes a story to tell and a setting pleasant enough for hosting, with genuine “aesthetic reflection” (attractiveness creator) around the farm;
- sufficient theoretical and practical knowledge of what can be done within the scope of agritourism;
- mastery of communication skills to promote their farm and agritourism offer, including proficiency in digital tools to ensure information accessibility (location, opening hours, etc.);
- the ability to show hospitality, which implies appreciation of human contact: “you have to be willing to work with tourists” (institutional actor), “you have to like people” (farmer);
- mastery of facilitation skills to showcase their agritourism product to groups while also setting limits;
- adaptability skills to remain flexible in responding to consumer demand;
- language proficiency, especially in English, to interact with foreign tourists.

However, the acquisition of these human and commercial skills varies widely among farmers. In the sample, half of the farmers felt they did not master them sufficiently. Older farmers, in particular, often lacked interpersonal skills (facilitation, hospitality). “You need to be open to this kind of thing, us Latvians, we are not so open” (farmer). This lack of interpersonal competence stems partly from the stigma of the Soviet era, when people had to be “more cautious about everything, to survive” (promoter). Forced collectivization left a deep imprint on farmers' openness to cooperation. For them, “tourism may sometimes appear unfamiliar, even intimidating” (promoter). This attitude can be related to the concept of hypernormalization, as defined by Russian historian Yurchak in 2005 (Qazi, 2024). In

response to the dysfunctions of hypernormal Soviet society, individuals adopted passivity and immobility out of fear of the risks associated with change, an attitude they maintain despite growing difficulties.

It is also noteworthy that only 4 out of 10 interviewed farmers identified farmers themselves as key actors in agritourism development. They thus failed to fully acknowledge their own importance in these dynamics, even though they are at the very center of them (by creating and offering the tourism product), whereas other actors better understood their central role (cited by 12/17). Moreover, many farmers are introverted, and tourism may be perceived as an intrusion into the tranquility they seek in their natural surroundings. As a result, developing such skills, or more generally, an agritourism activity, is not a priority for them.

For these farms, the main objective remains production. Yet production itself faces multiple obstacles: 4/10 farmers reported difficulties linked to bureaucracy; 3/10 mentioned weather-related challenges (“it’s always too dry, or too cold, or too hot”, “the main problem we face is cold winters and unstable weather conditions”); 3/10 cited legislative instability (“the rules change every year”); 3/10 faced financial difficulties; 3/10 lacked labor; and 2/10 reported issues linked to sanitary management of the farm. These obstacles are consistent with the entrepreneurial barriers identified by the OECD in 2019 to rural economic development in Latvia: bureaucratic inefficiency (19% of responses), tax levels (18%) and tax regulations (13%), as well as corruption (9%), shortage of unskilled labor (8.2%), policy instability (8%), and lack of financing (8%). These pressures weigh heavily on production, which remains the backbone of farm economies. The pressure is even greater under this model, where the farm is both the production tool and the farmer’s home. Thus, the risk is not only entrepreneurial but also personal, since it may jeopardize a family and generational home.

Against this backdrop, agritourism can impose additional constraints on production. “Many farmers already have too much work to do, they don’t have time to organize agritourism activities” (institutional actor). Organizing agritourism requires additional resources (time, labor), brings further standards and administrative burdens, and carries no guarantee of increased sales. Consequently, farmers unaccustomed to such activities cannot simply be forced into them: “you cannot expect someone who has been growing carrots for 40 years to suddenly start making TikToks” (restaurateur).

In this regard, the younger generation represents an important lever. During the Covid-19 crisis, many young people returned to the countryside and were able to share experiences with the older generation. In several cases, they provided the knowledge needed to launch tourism activities on family farms. In general, the younger generation is more open to cooperation, opportunities, and visitors. Whereas the older generation typically speaks Latvian and Russian, the younger generation speaks Latvian and English, sometimes German. They are more capable of organizing agritourism activities and represent a trusted source of additional labor for older farmers. After the lockdowns, a number of young people remained on family farms, though not all had this opportunity. Furthermore, although the younger generation is indeed a lever for agritourism development in family farms due to their skills and openness, it is important to situate this dynamic within the broader context of generational renewal challenges faced by the sector (Cossin, 2024).

Beyond these structural and generational obstacles, the development of agritourism is also constrained by issues of individual perception. Many actors display a form of “shameful pride” in their culture. On one hand, they are proud of it; on the other, they constantly

compare it with other cultures. Such comparison becomes a mechanism of self-depreciation and inferiorization. As one farmer put it: “you could go to Bordeaux to visit the vineyards, but to come to the Vidzeme to see the swamps...” Another expressed doubts about the potential for developing agritourism in Latvia, judging the country’s agricultural history less interesting than that of other foreign countries.

Despite these systemic barriers and drivers, the bioregional agritourism system is by no means homogeneous. A territorial approach is therefore required to better understand it.

II.2. Contrasting intra-bioregional territorial dynamics

A more detailed analysis at the territorial scale highlights sharper contrasts that influence the development of agritourism within the bioregion.

II.2.a. The bioregion as a scale of cooperation struggling to secure the commitment of certain agritourism stakeholders

Only two-thirds of the stakeholders interviewed express a sense of belonging to the bioregion ([Table 6](#)). Among the reasons cited, 11 stakeholders refer to projects, actions, or values promoted by the bioregion that align with their own: “the values correspond to my personal values” (attractiveness creator). These values revolve around organic farming, biodiversity and environmental protection, circular economy, support for local businesses, tourism development, and food waste reduction. Another 11 stakeholders describe a sense of belonging through professional ties, linked to activities shared between the bioregion and their own business or institution. Ten stakeholders portray the bioregion as an opportunity for exchange. It is defined as “a place of open-mindedness” (promoter), fostering dialogue among various actors across the territory: professionals (including organic farmers), citizens, and even schools. It is described as a place of integration where knowledge and skills can be shared with other stakeholders who recognize the importance of nature. In this sense, the bioregion nurtures both a sense of belonging and usefulness, while contributing to community well-being. “I am a convinced patriot of this place” (farmer). Finally, six stakeholders emphasize their rootedness in the bioregion, having been born there, and their attachment to the local culture with which they identify. They see the bioregion as a tool to enhance their living environment and quality of life. It is worth noting that two stakeholders feel a sense of belonging to the bioregion without actually living within it: a farmer from Ogre municipality who shares the values around organic farming promoted by the bioregion, and an institutional actor living in the Zemgale region but working in the national park.

Yet one-third of the stakeholders interviewed, mainly farmers, do not feel a sense of belonging to the bioregion. The main reason, cited by four respondents, is the lack of concrete actions implemented: “there is no physical action” (farmer). As the bioregion remains a recent initiative, these actors do not perceive any significant change compared to the past. Two farmers in the northern part of Valmiera municipality, located in the Vidzeme North Biosphere, feel excluded from the dynamics of the bioregion, despite belonging to one of the three municipalities that signed the memorandum: “I like this idea, what they are

doing... but this bioregion is mostly for Cēsis and Valmiera.” Two other farmers located on the edge of the national park had never even heard of the bioregion: “I am not entirely sure what a bioregion is,” admitted one of them. Rather than identifying with the bioregion, these stakeholders express affiliations that range from the local (“I am a local patriot,” said a farmer) to the national, often embracing multiple scales (local, regional, national).

Table 6 – Sense of belonging to the bioregion by stakeholder category (author, 2025)

Belonging / Stakeholder category	Farmers	Other service providers	Institutional actors	Promoters	Attractiveness creators	Total
Yes	3	1	10	2	2	18
No	7	0	0	1	1	9

This lack of identification with the bioregion may hinder the development of strategies at the bioregional scale. This is particularly significant given that the absence of belonging is most prevalent among farmers, actors who nevertheless play a pivotal role in agritourism development. This sentiment also brings to light another reality: the polarization of territorial dynamics between urban centers and rural areas.

I.2.b. A polarization of economic, social and touristic dynamics by urban centers with strong identities, connected by nature, leading to inequalities between urban and rural areas

Economic, social and touristic activity in the bioregion is concentrated around the municipalities urban centers ([Figure 9](#)):

▫ **Sigulda:** A suburban city of Riga that is highly attractive, easily accessible by transport (particularly by train), and drawing many young families thanks to advantageous taxation⁴. Sigulda is renowned for family-friendly leisure activities, such as outdoor and winter sports (skiing, bobsleigh). It also has a recognized historical heritage with its three castles (the new and old castles of Sigulda, and the nearby Turaida castle).

▫ **Cēsis:** A culturally significant city in Latvia, located in the heart of Gauja National Park. Cēsis is recognized for its well-preserved historical and cultural heritage. Numerous cultural activities are organized in the city, such as concerts and festivals, including the LAMPA festival (of national importance), during which many experts are invited to publicly debate on a variety of topics.

▫ **Valmiera:** An industrial city that succeeded in maintaining and revitalizing its economic activity after the collapse of the USSR. Valmiera is considered the regional capital of Vidzeme, and is a major hub of employment and education for the inhabitants of Vidzeme. Less touristic than Sigulda and Cēsis, it nevertheless attracts visitors through the organization of sporting events and its natural heritage.

⁴ It was mentioned in several interviews that the municipality of Sigulda has a program aimed at reducing the tax rate for families with young children in order to encourage them to settle in the municipality.

These urban centers, particularly Sigulda and Cēsis, are considered as offering “one of the best situations in Latvia” (attractiveness creator). It is said that “there is a prestige in living here” (attractiveness creator), and that “everything you need for a normal life is nearby” (promoter). Located less than two hours from Riga, these cities welcome new residents who commute daily to the capital through a phenomenon of pendular migration identified in the literature (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment”, 2023). Contextually, Covid also contributed to the expansion of remote work, and many Riga residents took the opportunity to relocate to the countryside. As a result, these cities are becoming increasingly attractive, leading to localized demographic growth, as observed in Sigulda where this growth translates into urban sprawl.

Main tourist attraction areas as identified by the stakeholders interviewed in the Gauja National Park and its immediate surroundings
(Glatoud, n=24, based on OpenStreetMap, 2025)

Figure 9 - Map of tourist attractiveness zones as designated by interviewed stakeholders (author, 2025)

For these cities, tourism is described as a “strategic industry” (institutional actor). Sigulda, for example, is called “the capital of tourism in Latvia” (institutional actor) as well as “the little Switzerland” (institutional actor). However, this tourism is subject to several constraints. The seasonality of tourism, already mentioned, limits activity in winter. Furthermore, during the lockdown, some businesses closed and were unable to reopen. The proximity to the Russian border and frequent threats also discourage visitors: “foreign tourists are afraid of what might happen” (farmer), “people see this region as a risk zone” (institutional actor). These cities are interconnected by the Gauja valley, a natural feature and one of the main tourist attractions of the park, complementing the touristic offer of these three cities. It offers picturesque landscapes, as well as a wide range of nature-based activities: trails, hiking, wildlife observation, water sports...

Nature itself is by far the main element used by stakeholders to describe the identity of their territory (24/27 mention it). It is articulated as a homogeneous identity web linking these cities with strong individual identities, through several symbols: the biocenosis, particularly the biotope (forests, northern marshes) which provides untouched and wild nature, telluric elements such as relief (Gauja valley, hills) and geology (sandstone cliffs, heterogeneous

soils), and water-related features (rivers, lakes). In the north of the bioregion, another natural park exists, the Salacas park, located within the North Vidzeme Biosphere Reserve.

Nevertheless, this nature is not only visual. Fourteen out of twenty-seven actors mention positively perceived values attributed to it: “it is something symbolic” (promoter). Nature is linked to the cultural identity of the region, rooted in traditions, a healthy lifestyle, and appreciation of environmental beauty that contributes to local pride. Nature is also associated with tranquility: calm, harmony, well-being, safety, cleanliness, and low population density. It is a space of leisure and recreation, recognized for its accessibility. Finally, it is a place of social connection, carrying memories (childhood, family, friends) and a sense of community.

Heritage, cited by 16/27 actors, is also an element of territorial identity. This heritage is embodied in the cities (“visiting Sigulda, Cēsis, it is always a delight for the eyes” said an attractiveness creator), but also in rural areas with castles, churches, manor houses... Some villages contribute to this heritage, such as Līgatne (with its old paper mill, a legacy of Soviet industry) along the Gauja between Sigulda and Cēsis, Straupe with its medieval castle on the edge of the park, or Rūjiena and Mazsalaca north of Valmiera near the Salacas park. In addition to tangible heritage, the bioregion enjoys a significant intangible traditional heritage: know-how, craftsmanship, festivals, songs, dances... A gallery is available in [Appendix 3](#) illustrating the natural and heritage elements of the territory. An institutional actor aptly summarized the identity of their territory: “for me, a home territory is not defined by a single characteristic. It is born from the harmony between people, nature and culture.” There is no immobility in the landscape, which reinforces the idea of interconnection through nature.

It is in this natural context that agriculture develops, mentioned by 13/27 actors as an element of territorial identity. It is associated with small-scale family farms, and with the history of the region. It is also linked to healthy food, less dependent on pesticides. Agriculture contributes to the authenticity of rural areas and reinforces their attractiveness. According to stakeholders, agriculture tends to be the third or fourth economic sector depending on the municipality, behind tourism, manufacturing or forestry. However, it is the leading sector in rural territories, despite its low added value at municipal scale. It represents a subsistence economic activity: “it is the first thing to make money” (farmer). Agriculture creates jobs in rural areas, but these are precarious, with lower wages than in other sectors and physically demanding. This reinforces the idea of polarization of activity by urban centers.

This polarization leads to inequalities between urban and rural areas. Due to recent contextual elements, the Latvian economy has been weakened: “things are bad right now, the economy is stagnating” (attractiveness creator). Many foreign investors (Russian, European) have withdrawn from the Latvian market. The consequence is strong inflation, particularly on food products, combined with stagnating wages, leading to a decline in consumer purchasing power. According to interviews, these economic difficulties are particularly severe in rural areas where agriculture dominates. In these territories, tourism is not as developed as in urban centers, and its importance is questioned: “here, it is extremely important, on a scale from 1 to 10, it is 10” (institutional actor) versus “tourism is not as profitable as agriculture” (farmer). These territories face a loss of attractiveness: expansion of large farms at the expense of small and medium-sized family farms, difficult working

This lack of tourist infrastructure is also visible on farms. Technically, among the interviewed farmers, 9/10 possess infrastructures that could serve agritourism activities (Table 7), and the only one who has none has already considered developing a sales building. However, this information should be nuanced. Although the majority own infrastructures that could be used for agritourism, they are not currently used as such in the normal operation of the farm (they represent a potential that could be mobilized). Moreover, when looking at the quality of these infrastructures, the only one mostly represented is a basic reception facility: the visitor area. Amenities and operational infrastructures are much less common. Also, only one farm has a paved parking lot, which raises questions about their physical accessibility.

Table 7 – Type and number of tourist infrastructures present on the visited farms (author, 2025)

Type of infrastructure	/9	Type of infrastructure	/9
Farm visitor area	5	Sales building	3
Toilets (outside home)	3	Accommodation facility	2
Event building	2	Camping area (tents)	2
Paved parking	1	Restaurant facility	1

[Basic reception infrastructure; Amenities; Operational infrastructures]

Some farms are difficult to locate. There is sometimes a lack of signage indicating their location, making the use of internet necessary, which can be difficult in white zones: “you feel anxious traveling in a territory where you are not connected to the rest of the world” (farmer). Road conditions are also a major challenge for accessibility, described as “the number one problem people complain about” and “the main reason why agritourism does not develop” (institutional actors). In 2015, 45% of the country’s roads were still unpaved (gravel, stones...) (OECD, 2019). While road conditions are satisfactory on main routes and near cities, their quality decreases the further away one goes, and they are less well maintained. Depending on the season, they can be muddy and boggy, snowy and icy, or dusty and gravelly. Significant damage is also caused by forestry activity and its heavy machinery (Figure 11). Because of this situation, tourist buses refuse to access these farms. Although this issue of roads is central in public debate, the lack of municipal resources and workload are obstacles to current reconstruction programs. For example, the municipality of Cēsis has a reconstruction program but it is limited to two roads per parish per year.

Figure 11 - Photos of damages on rural roads (author, 2025)

Soft mobility is also not an effective means to reach farms. In Latvia, the most used mode of transport by tourists remains the car (87.3%), against only 12.7% for soft mobility (bus, train, bicycle) (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024b). By bicycle, one needs to be in good physical shape to reach the most remote farms. Cyclists can struggle on poorly maintained roads, which can be dangerous in winter. Several stakeholders mentioned a lack of bike paths: bicycles share roads with cars where the speed limit is generally 90 km/h. “It’s too dangerous!” stated a farmer. Cyclists may also be exposed to dog attacks. Cities are connected to Riga by train and bus, but this connectivity decreases once further away. “In some small villages in the bioregion, there are buses twice a day, and that is not enough to visit” (promoter), or even once a week: “you can go one day, and return the following week” (institutional actor). One must also consider the distance between the bus stop and the farm in question, which may require walking several kilometers. This is particularly problematic for elderly people or those with reduced mobility. “This last-kilometer connection remains a challenge” (institutional actor).

The development of these infrastructures is a real issue. Latvia is a small country, so these infrastructures are largely sufficient for the current domestic demand. However, they are not adapted to a larger demand, particularly in rural areas, which may hinder the increase of tourist flows into these territories. Such development would require significant investment. As one institutional actor pointed out: “nobody wants to take responsibility for toilets, it costs a lot of money.” Due to insufficient demand in these territories, there is reluctance to invest, which is particularly damaging for them. As one actor observed, the lack of initial investment leads to a vicious circle: “because there is no demand, there are no attractions, and because there are no attractions, there is no demand” (restaurateur). Yet, it is in these struggling rural territories that bioregional agriculture is concentrated, forming the basis for the elaboration of local products.

II.3. Limited valorization of local products and their specificities, hindering their accessibility to tourists

In line with the idea of using agritourism as a means of socio-economic valorization of local production, the study of these local products and the current state of their promotion reveals goods with relevant specificities, highly demanded by tourists, yet insufficiently accessible.

II.3.a. A poorly defined local product, but with relevant specificities clearly identified by agritourism stakeholders

Latvians have a strong attachment to their gastronomy and local products (Stankevica, 2023). Food is not only a cultural component but also part of their heritage. A consumer survey conducted by Rimi shows that one quarter of respondents associate the “taste of Latvia” with their parents’ cuisine. The transmission and celebration of culinary practices takes on an almost patriotic dimension. However, there is no consensus whatsoever regarding the definition of what constitutes “local,” and interpretations vary considerably.

The geographical approach, particularly the territorial one, is the main component cited by stakeholders when defining a local product. Yet, the scale of the territory considered varies widely (Table 8). Due to the country’s small size, some stakeholders even combine several scales in their definition, often associating a smaller scale (village, municipality) with a broader one (regional, national). Still within the geographical perspective, three stakeholders adopted an aterritorial approach to defining local products, i.e., proximity between the buyer and the place of production, regardless of administrative boundaries.

The axiological approach also emerges as an important component cited by stakeholders in defining local products. Seven stakeholders state that a local product must have a story (linked to family, traditions, or know-how). Two stakeholders emphasize transparency in production methods, while two others insist on environmental cooperation and respect. One stakeholder believes a local product should not be industrial, while another associates it with the values of the bioregion. Less frequently mentioned, the socio-economic approach was also cited: two stakeholders argue that a local product should reinvest capital into the national economic system, and one stakeholder defines it as a product sold at local markets (as opposed to supermarkets).

Table 8 – Territorial scale considered as “local” for a product, according to interviewed stakeholders (author, 2025)

Territorial scale of the “local” product	Number of responses
Village and its surroundings	3
Municipality	2
Gauja national park	1
Bioregion	3
Vidzeme region	5
Latvia	7
Baltic states	1

This lack of a shared definition of “local” can be problematic when attempting to enhance the value of local products. Nevertheless, while stakeholders’ practical definitions of local products diverge significantly, their views converge when it comes to identifying product specificities.

The main characteristic of local products, cited by 17 out of 27 stakeholders, is their diversity: “The strong point is that there are many different products” (institutional actor). Examples include bakery goods (rye bread, pastries, gingerbread), vegetables (pumpkin, asparagus, cabbage, carrot, etc.), berries (blueberry, redcurrant, blackcurrant, gooseberry, sea buckthorn, rowan, strawberry, cloudberry, etc.), fruits (apple, pear, quince), consumed fresh, dried, or processed into juices and jams, meats (beef, lamb, poultry, etc.), fish (such as the labeled Burtnieks pike-perch and other freshwater fish), dairy products (milk, cow or goat cheese, Rūjiena ice cream), fermented products (Valmiera beer, artisanal wines, lacto-fermented vegetables), herbal teas made from aromatic and medicinal plants, honey, wool products, and more.

Beyond diversity, other specificities were identified:

- ✧ 12/27 stakeholders highlight the human connection these products foster, with small-scale farms enabling exchanges with producers and a better understanding of how products are made: “you see the passion in their eyes and their hearts” (restaurateur); “it’s like a personal relationship, I can trust them” (institutional actor).

- ✧ 11/27 mention taste qualities (flavor, aroma, texture, smell).

- ✧ 9/27 emphasize craftsmanship and authenticity: “they have their own story” (institutional actor).

- ✧ 9/27 underline the healthy and natural qualities of these products, respectful of the environment and free from chemicals.

- ✧ 6/27 point to their freshness, thanks to seasonal production marketed quickly after harvest: “this seasonality reinforces their authenticity and their link with nature” (promoter).

- ✧ 6/27 stress traceability (locally produced and processed).

Yet, despite these qualities, the local valorization of such products remains difficult.

II.3.b. A lack of mutual understanding among different actors in the supply chain limiting the promotion of local products and their valorization through short supply chains

Local products are generally sold at higher prices than imported ones for two main reasons. First, small and medium-sized bioregional farms operate under a less productivist model. Their lower production volumes result in higher unit prices to offset increased production costs. Second, retailers often apply higher profit margins to local products compared to other types of goods. In addition, many local products are high value-added goods. This type of product represents a national objective and is one of the priorities of the Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy 2030 (LIBRA) (Aļeksējeva, 2024).

Nevertheless, the main market segment interested in local and organic products consists of rural residents and individuals with lower levels of education (Naglis-Liepa et al., 2022). They perceive these products as a way of preserving a traditional lifestyle and of being involved in agriculture. Their consumption reflects prosocial values such as supporting local culture and

preserving the environment. For rural populations, personal contact with the seller is also more important than for urban residents, given the smaller size of communities.

However, the notion of “local product” remains poorly understood by many consumers, especially urban ones, despite having greater purchasing power and being more capable of buying such goods. For them, the concepts of “local” and “organic” are unclear and frequently confused. “Latvians say: if it’s organic then it’s Latvian” (institutional actor). There is a lack of food education among these populations, who feel little or no pride or sense of belonging with respect to their local products. Among wealthier classes, there even seems to be a form of “snobbery,” with consumers preferring foreign goods deemed more prestigious: “Latvians are sometimes ashamed of themselves, they buy champagne because they think it looks cool, they do not understand the value of their products” (farmer); “we are not so loyal Latvians” (farmer).

With rising prices, buying local products has become even more difficult. Prices of vegetables and meats (lamb, goat, poultry, beef and veal, pork) have seen the steepest inflation over the past four years (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024a), though the increase has also affected the entire consumption basket (cereals, potatoes, dairy products, etc.). Faced with purchasing power constraints, consumers tend to prioritize price over origin: “they look for cheaper products, not necessarily the best quality” (promoter); “in general, people don’t care about quality, most are only concerned with price” (farmer).

Thus, there is a mutual lack of understanding: some consumers fail to see why local products are more expensive and what qualities justify the price, sometimes even lacking trust in them (Aļeksējeva, 2024); on the other side, some producers fail to understand consumers’ budgetary constraints in order to adapt their supply. Overall awareness of the importance of sustainable food for both the local economy and public health remains insufficient to date, limiting the establishment of short supply chains in the Vidzeme region (Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2024). Still, this relationship cannot be fully generalized, as some farmers are aware of consumers’ financial difficulties and try to adapt their practices accordingly. Yet many farmers lack knowledge and cooperative networks to share information, which complicates the marketing of local products both to consumers and to other actors in the supply chain ([Figure 12](#)).

Figure 12 - Diagram of trends in the bioregional supply chain (author, 2025, based on Aleksējeva, 2024; Cossin, 2024; Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2024)

In this supply chain, bioregional farmers sell to tourism-related service providers (restaurants, local shops) as well as to local markets capable of attracting tourists. Local businesses represent a significant market, with, for example, 404 commercial catering enterprises (restaurants, cafés, etc.) operating in the Vidzeme region (Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2024). However, difficulties of mutual understanding persist, with 8 out of 10 farmers reporting challenges in supplying local businesses.

Among these, five emphasize a mismatch between producers' offerings and the demands of the commercial catering sector. The main issue lies in requested volumes, which are often too small. The lack of centralization and aggregation in supply results in a fragmented system requiring time and labor resources that many farmers do not have. "Logistics are different for them" (farmer). The interviewed restaurateur also lamented the absence of such intermediary enterprises outside Riga. In Sigulda municipality, there is one company (Ekologisks) that centralizes and aggregates production from small and medium-sized farms for public catering services, but this company did not respond to interview requests. For livestock farmers, low demand may also create difficulties with carcass balance. One farmer mentioned the lack of flexibility among restaurants that fail to take seasonality into account. Additionally, three farmers highlighted an overall lack of demand from local businesses, which already have suppliers or show little interest in local products or their value: "there is a mentality problem" (farmer).

Latvia is also facing a concerning increase in overweight and obesity rates, linked to a diet dominated by processed foods rich in additives and sugar (Latvijas Lauku konsultāciju un izglītības centrs, 2021). In this context, public health objectives, along with the reduction of dependence on Polish imports, make the development of organic farming and short supply chains central in many policies and projects. Within the Farm to Fork strategy, Latvia has launched a reflection process on structuring green public procurement to enable supply for public catering (especially schools and kindergartens). This also aims to raise children's awareness of food and to foster changes in consumption habits (Aļeksējeva, 2024).

Green public procurement had already come into force in Latvia on July 1, 2017, becoming mandatory for such institutions. These procurement rules notably required: 50% of milk and kefir, and 20% of cereals to be certified organic. Addressing these issues has highlighted the growing need for a regional food strategy in Vidzeme (Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2024). This need will be integrated into the trans-Baltic KISMET project, which aims to develop a food strategy for Vidzeme (currently lacking), based on evidence-driven data and recommendations for implementing the Farm to Fork strategy. The region has already set up a collaborative platform enabling involved actors to co-decide on shared objectives. These actors include: producers, food industry companies, catering enterprises, event organizers, Vidzeme municipalities, educational and research institutions, state institutions, support structures and financial management bodies, representatives of distribution chains, NGOs and interest groups, and LAGs.

Local markets also play an important role in strengthening cooperation and connecting farmers. For example, the Valmiera market was frequently cited for its participation in the Finnish REKO movement, which promotes fair trade in support of short supply chains. Despite these efforts, however, the promotion of local products remains limited and their accessibility restricted, particularly for tourists.

II.3.c. A mismatch between tourists' willingness to purchase local products and their accessibility

The difficulties linked to supplying local businesses limit the accessibility of local products in areas where tourism dynamics are concentrated (see [Figure 9](#), p. 29). These products are hard to find in shops, which do not always highlight them sufficiently among other goods, and they are almost impossible to find in supermarkets. Some restaurants may offer them, but the most reliable way to access such products remains local markets or festivals. Yet, tourists represent an interesting clientele, as they are willing to pay more for a quality local product. Purchases and food consumption are estimated to be the second and third largest categories of tourist expenditure after transport, representing 23.5% and 19.5% of their spending respectively (Centrālā statistikas pārvalde, 2024b).

A total of 25 out of 27 interviewed actors believe that tourists (not only agritourists) are actively looking for local products during their stay: "everyone wants to buy a local product" (farmer). This demand exists at municipal tourism centers, among domestic as well as international tourists: "there are many examples of Estonians, they are always looking for local products" (promoter). Tourists seek original souvenirs or experiences related to

products in order to enrich their overall visit: “they understand the value of local products” (institutional actor). For some, purchasing local products is also a way to support producers.

They also have specific expectations for these local products: they must be authentic, come with a story, and be embedded in traditions transmitted across generations. Products must be local in both production and processing, made from territorial resources, and carry a “local touch” (institutional actor). “They are looking for something unique” (attractiveness creator), or something new (taste, appearance), with quality superior to supermarket products: “quality products that stand out from the rest” (farmer). Tourists value more natural products, free of additives or ultra-processing, as well as the possibility of seeing where and by whom the product was made (transparency and traceability). They may also seek recommended or prestigious goods. Regarding price, affordability is preferable, though some tourists are willing to pay more if their expectations are met. Overall, these expectations align with the specificities of local products highlighted earlier.

Convenience, however, has been identified as an important determinant of food purchasing behavior (Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2024). Since local products are concentrated outside tourist hubs, it is necessary to provide clear information so that consumers can find and identify them. National legislation requires stores to indicate the country of origin of products, thus facilitating the identification of national goods. Quality labels have also been developed to enhance the promotion of national products. The “Green Spoon” (Zaļā karotīte) label indicates that the product meets quality criteria and that at least 75% of raw materials are of national origin. Similarly, the “Bordeaux Spoon” (Bordo karotīte) label goes further by certifying that the product was entirely produced and processed nationally.

The digital market Novada Garša, developed by LLKC, organizes an annual national competition in which a jury evaluates small-scale producers’ goods according to several quality criteria (taste, smell, etc.). Winners receive a “regional taste” label (gold, silver, or bronze category). Municipalities also have their own labels certifying the geographical origin and quality of products, which they actively use as promotional tools for tourists. Promoters such as tourism centers or EnterGauja also provide information about where to buy or taste local products.

Local heritage, especially gastronomic heritage, is another medium through which local products are promoted. Attractiveness creators such as local markets and festivals do not only sell local products but place them at the center of their communication strategies, greatly benefiting their visibility. In terms of gastronomy, the Home Café Days, organized annually by LIAA in cooperation with Lauku Ceļotājs, allow rural territories to host pop-up restaurants for two days between July and September. These temporary restaurants are opened by local residents, who showcase traditional cuisine and promote local products to tourists. In 2017, the Riga-Gauja region was named European Region of Gastronomy by the International Institute of Gastronomy, Culture, Arts, and Tourism. This nomination marked an important milestone in ambitions to develop gastronomic tourism in the area.

Producers themselves (individually or through associations) also play an active role in promoting local products. They organize activities around their goods, increasingly use social media, and sometimes directly approach service providers (restaurants, tourism organizers) to gain better visibility and recommendations among tourists.

Despite these efforts, actors (regardless of category) believe local products could be better promoted (Table 9). “You really have to search for them” (attractiveness creator).

Table 9 – Responses of interviewed actors to the question: “Do you think local products are sufficiently promoted today?” (author, 2025)

Responses	Number of responses
Yes	5
Yes <i>but...</i>	10
No	12

Several obstacles to the promotion of local products were raised. Some actors argue that there is a lack of information on local products themselves, their specificities, and the people who produce them (and their stories). Furthermore, no coordinated promotion exists among municipalities for bioregional products, and several actors noted insufficient international communication: “one of the difficulties of the bioregion is that it is mainly formed by three municipalities, each already with its own brand” (institutional actor).

Labels were also questioned. Some actors feel municipalities do not capitalize enough on their potential, while others criticize the lack of more concrete and demanding criteria to obtain them: “it doesn’t mean anything” (farmer). Others underline the absence of a bioregional label. Cost is also a concern: municipalities would like producers to take a more active role in promoting their products, particularly by developing digital skills, but producers cite difficulties in mobilizing resources (money, time, labor) in addition to their daily work, and wish for stronger municipal support.

Farmers nevertheless appear interested in selling their products to tourists. Among the 10 interviewed farmers, 7 expressed such interest: “of course we would want to!” (farmer). Specifically, four would like to sell more to restaurants, one would like to sell more directly to tourists on the farm, and another would like to sell more on other farms. The three farmers not interested gave different reasons: current limitations of the tourist market, logistical constraints in the supply chain, and an already established customer base that makes additional outlets unnecessary.

These interviews thus revealed, by crossing the perspectives of 27 interviewed actors with existing literature, a set of **barriers** limiting the development of the bioregional agritourism system:

- a lack of structuring and coordination among actors (no consensus on the definition of agritourism, multiplicity of uncoordinated initiatives, lack of mutual knowledge among actors, lack of data);
- human and psychological barriers (stigma of collectivization, hyper-normalization, lack of skills, entrepreneurial priority-setting, weak sense of belonging to the bioregion, lack of mutual understanding among actors);
- territorial inequalities (polarization of activity around urban areas, depopulation and declining attractiveness of rural areas);
- insufficient infrastructure (limited rural tourism facilities, difficult physical access to farms, lack of on-farm infrastructure);
- limited accessibility of local products (no consensus on the definition of “local,” fragmented supply chain, difficulties in providing tourists with information on products and their specificities).

However, the interviews also highlighted several **drivers** for developing this bioregional agritourism system:

- a strong territorial identity (landscapes, values linked to nature, tangible and intangible heritage, agriculture, local products);
- existing development opportunities (funding, training offers, mentoring programs, cooperation initiatives, promotional opportunities);
- favorable contextual factors (revitalization of the “local,” growing attractiveness of rural cities, supportive development policies, openness and skills of the new generation);
- existing, clearly identified demand and an emerging supply in line with this demand (the agritourist profile and expectations, demand for local products from tourists and their expectations, emerging initiatives aligned with these expectations).

The identification of these barriers and drivers, combined with the expectations of interviewed actors and literature, provided the foundation for developing three strategies aimed at fostering the development of the bioregional agritourism system.

III. Towards a defined, organized, and sustainable bioregional agritourism system

The three strategies identified following these results concern the need to define the bioregional agritourism system, to organize it, and to ensure its long-term sustainability.

III.1. The need to define the agritourism system in order to move from microcosms to an attractive tourist destination

The absence of consensus on the definition of agritourism and local products, the associated difficulties in promotion, and the weak sense of belonging among stakeholders to the bioregion currently hinder the emergence of a bioregional agritourism destination. Yet, the strong territorial identity, the clearly identified and growing demand for agritourism and local products, as well as the initial offers already aligned with this demand, represent solid levers to consolidate this system. To move beyond the organizational microcosms that currently compose the agritourism system and to enable the emergence of an attractive destination, it is therefore necessary to more clearly define certain components: its territory, its key assets to be promoted, and its stakeholders.

III.1.a. Defining the physical territory and questioning the geographical boundaries of the bioregion

The sense of belonging to the bioregion varies and remains rather weak among farmers. This calls into question the scale at which agritourism should be developed, particularly at the current bioregional scale. If agritourism is to be developed at this level, then the geographical boundaries of the bioregion must be discussed in order to successfully build a sense of territorial identity. By definition, a bioregion does not only refer to geographical elements but also to “cognitive” ones, that is; it is the result of a natural environment combined with socio-cultural elements that evolve within it. However, today the Gauja bioregion is defined primarily by administrative boundaries that poorly reflect the sense of belonging felt by local actors.

To create a bioregional sense of place, it is necessary to geographically define this bioregion based on mobilizable territorial elements (natural and heritage features, infrastructure, farms) that share a set of common values around which local actors feel a sense of belonging. A first idea would be to reduce the bioregional perimeter to the Gauja national park, but this would limit agritourism development possibilities, since actors located in the periphery also hold relevant agritourism assets worth highlighting. A second option would therefore be to enlarge the bioregional territory. For instance, one farmer located in the municipality of Ogre expressed this sense of belonging without being part of the three municipalities that signed the memorandum. Others, situated in the northern part of Valmiera municipality, believe the bioregion is overly centered around Gauja national park and feel more connected to the North Vidzeme Biosphere Reserve ([Figure 13](#)).

Figure 13 – Map of the location of the North Vidzeme Biosphere Reserve in Latvia (OECD, 2019. in Anzaldúa et al., 2022)

This biosphere reserve, shared between the municipalities of Valmiera, Valka, and Limbaži (Druva-Druvaskalne & Livina, 2008), constitutes an interesting territory towards which the bioregion could expand. It possesses mobilizable elements with which local actors identify and which share similar values to those found in Gauja national park. It is the largest protected area in Vidzeme, with a surface of 475,514 ha (compared to 91,750 ha for Gauja) (Anzaldúa et al., 2022). The biosphere includes 25 nature reserves, 1 national park (Salacas), and 2 marine reserves, and shares the same environmental standards as Gauja (Dabas aizsardzības pārvalde, 2024). Moreover, while Valka municipality has only 12% of its area under organic farming, Limbaži reaches 30% (Ozola, 2025). It could strengthen the bioregion's landscape diversity thanks to its lakes, marshes, and access to the Baltic Sea via the Gulf of Riga (Figure 14). It is also a transnational territory (Dabas aizsardzības pārvalde, 2024), partially located in Estonia, with a rapidly developing rural tourism sector attracting both domestic and foreign visitors (Druva-Druvaskalne & Livina, 2008). Linking the two areas could therefore create territorial continuity between southern Estonia and Gauja, generating an uninterrupted tourist flow that could foster increased foreign demand around Gauja national park.

Figure 14 – Landscape of Ainaži, a border village in Limbaži municipality (author, 2025)

Although this rapprochement with the biosphere remains hypothetical, the need for Gauja's bioregion to connect with neighboring territories is essential to building a genuine bioregional identity around mobilizable assets. A first possible step would be to connect with the northern part of Valmiera municipality, included in the biosphere, which is not currently perceived by local actors as bioregional. Nevertheless, expanding to other territories would encounter several obstacles. On the one hand, the three municipalities currently forming the bioregion show limited interest in integrating external territories into bioregional development projects if they fall outside their administrative borders. On the other hand, these other territories may have local economic and social dynamics different from those observed in this study, which must be understood in order to assess the potential impact of agritourism development on local sectors. Dialogue between municipalities (both within the current bioregion and its surrounding areas) is therefore essential, as it would help identify how a bioregional territory could be constructed by pooling their individual resources and attractions into a diversified agritourism basket.

III.1.b. Defining the territorial brand identity through cohesive promotion of a consistent image

Territorial image and promotion are critical for agritourism development (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011). It is therefore necessary to clearly define the notions of agritourism and local products, and for these definitions to be widely acknowledged and shared by as many stakeholders as possible.

Since tourists have expectations both in terms of agritourism experiences and local products, promotion must align with these expectations in order to present an attractive brand identity that draws visitors to the territory (Kaže et al., 2011). Among the elements to be promoted are:

- nature (landscapes, biodiversity) and its associated values (escape, well-being, tranquility, etc.);
- authenticity of the experience through small- and medium-scale farms and direct contact with producers;
- roots and countryside traditions ;
- discovery of local products (history, know-how, specificities, quality);
- experiential activities and their distinctive features (originality, educational value, conviviality).

For the sake of coherence, a joint promotional strategy is needed, integrating both agritourism and local products, to allow easy identification of farms offering agritourism activities, their location, and the products available for purchase (including prices and specificities). This promotion must be clearly differentiated from other forms of rural tourism and complement the broader tourism offer (both rural and urban in the bioregion) in order to form a structured basket of goods and services (Mollard & Pecqueur, 2007). It must also be cohesive: if agritourism is to be developed at the bioregional scale, then promoters of the bioregion must collaborate to present a joint offer that integrates their locally attractive specificities, underscoring the importance of cooperation in the emergence of the agritourism system.

III.1.c. Defining stakeholders and highlighting the need for a more inclusive development of the agritourism system

At the end of their interviews, 22 out of 27 stakeholders reported that the process had led them to reflect on new ideas or questions they had not previously considered. This underscores a certain curiosity and a concrete interest in better understanding the subject. The interviews prompted 15 stakeholders to reflect more deeply on agritourism in general. This reflection covered diverse aspects: its definition, the intersectionality of its concept, potential support schemes for farmers, the need for more targeted and accessible promotion, the need for stronger cooperation among stakeholders, and the current lack of accessible data. They also encouraged 7 stakeholders, including 5 farmers, to consider the potential role of agritourism in their professional choices. Finally, 5 stakeholders began reflecting on the concept of a bioregion itself, its desired form, and its governance structure.

This curiosity and interest also translated into openness to collaboration. At the end of the survey, 27 out of 27 respondents declared themselves willing to collaborate more closely on issues related to agritourism. Seven of them believe that stronger collaboration around agritourism could generate mutual benefits for participating stakeholders and create positive externalities (e.g., increased wealth creation within the tourism system, greater awareness and preservation of nature, stronger promotion of the territory's identity and heritage). As one farmer noted, "everyone can benefit from it." For farmers, this could open up new opportunities, such as selling surplus production or sharing their personal story. Three out of ten farmers felt that stronger collaboration would facilitate the development of agritourism on their farms. It would help structure the offer (for example, through cooperation with tour operators), making agritourism less time-consuming to organize and freeing up more time for the primary production activity. It would also enable the mobilization of greater resources to better host tourists on the farm.

Despite this openness to collaboration, 4 out of 10 farmers interviewed are not engaged in organic farming. Yet, the bioregion is strongly oriented towards organic production, and numerous public policies aim to encourage its expansion (Aļeksējeva, 2024). Nevertheless, these farmers, in addition to their willingness to collaborate, possess highly relevant assets for agritourism development (particularly regarding their products and personal narratives). Thus, if agritourism is to be developed at the bioregional scale, it is essential to adopt an inclusive approach regarding which farmers are involved in the project.

This apparent openness should, however, be nuanced, since the response rate to interview requests was only 29%, and 59.1% of contacted stakeholders did not reply despite a median of two follow-up attempts per actor (see [Table 2](#), p. 15). It is possible that the favorable rate observed is due to bias, resulting from a pre-selection of actors already interested in agritourism, or curious enough to discuss it at the time of contact. Therefore, it is necessary to reach out to non-respondents in order to understand their reasons, as these may influence the viability of decision-making. Among these actors: farmers (despite being characteristic of typical agriculture, the sample included only 10 farmers, which is relatively few), other service providers whose response rate was extremely poor, local festivals, LAGs that did not reply, and Lauku Ceļotājs, given its important role in rural and agritourism development.

This need for inclusiveness in defining the stakeholders of the agritourism system simultaneously raises the question of governance and of the role that these actors should play within it.

III.2. The need for clear governance to efficiently organize the agritourism system and foster the development of initiatives

The study highlighted a lack of structuring, cooperation, and mutual knowledge among local actors, which reduces the effectiveness of development opportunities and support policies. These constraints are reinforced by psychological and human obstacles, as well as by the lack of tourism infrastructure in rural areas, which limits the emergence of initiatives around agritourism. In this context, the establishment of clear governance appears essential to efficiently organize the agritourism system and to foster the development of initiatives.

III.2.a. Diverging visions around current governance as a source of tensions

Before defining how the agritourism system should be organized, it is necessary to first listen to stakeholders' opinions on current governance, in order to understand how to structure the governance of the agritourism system. Stakeholders' level of satisfaction with rural development initiatives shows that many are aware of the barriers and drivers revealed in this study.

To date, local cooperation on tourism issues functions relatively well. Local actors seem to recognize the importance of working together ("we understand that we need each other," said one attractiveness creator), and openness to cooperation was mentioned as being greater than in other Latvian territories. However, some difficulties in cooperation were raised with local entrepreneurs. Farmers are considered too passive (due to the constraints already mentioned), while other service providers linked to tourism are perceived as too self-centered and focused on their own personal interests, and too closed off to collective approaches (such as scientific studies). This makes it difficult to develop coordinated strategies. This lack of engagement was also reflected in the study, as only one service provider has accepted to be interviewed.

More broadly, respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the way rural development initiatives are managed. Only 4 out of 27 were fully satisfied, and 13 out of 27 (less than half) expressed at least partial satisfaction (Table 10). Some stakeholders regretted the lack of consideration shown by municipalities for isolated rural areas and their specificities (related to polarization). They expressed a desire for municipal officials to better understand their personal difficulties. A farmer declared: “they don’t understand that I live in the countryside.” Another stated: “municipal politicians don’t understand that they should be proud of the products that locals produce [...]. These bureaucrats are always from the cities.” Another added: “sometimes I feel very alone in what I do.” The lack of cooperation among municipalities was also highlighted, particularly in terms of attracting tourists. “They are in competition for my choice [of destination], for the money I bring,” said an institutional actor.

Many stakeholders, especially institutional ones, regretted the lack of more active involvement from higher levels of government, which limits their ability to develop agritourism in the territory. Decision-making remains centralized in Riga, referred to as the “root of Latvia” by restaurant owner. This centralization marginalizes rural areas, which lack support. “There are actions where we would like things to move faster,” said an institutional actor. Worse still, this lack of consideration from the capital towards surrounding territories is perceived as condescending and dismissive: “they said they didn’t care about the countryside, you can imagine how people living there felt,” explained a farmer. Another farmer added: “sometimes it feels like our government is trying to punish us, and blames the European Union.” The lack of inter-ministerial cooperation was also criticized. Decisions on agritourism are made by the Ministry of Agriculture or the Ministry of Economy (responsible for tourism) without consultation between them. “It leads nowhere, there is a tragic lack of cooperation between ministries,” said an institutional actor; “maybe that’s the problem, because the ministry does not take charge of it, and that’s why agritourism is not developing,” said another.

The multiplicity of uncoordinated initiatives was also criticized. There is currently strong demand for strategies with a clear vision on several important issues (food strategy, agritourism strategy, etc.) in order to create more opportunities for rural territories. Current projects were criticized for their lack of results and concrete applications, as well as for being overly institutionalized. Regarding the bioregion, one attractiveness creator stated: “this bioregion is not for me,” implying that it does not sufficiently address issues rooted in the reality of their profession.

Table 10 – Stakeholders’ level of satisfaction with rural development initiatives, by category (author, 2025)

	Satisfied	Partially satisfied	Dissatisfied	No opinion
Farmers (/10)	2	3	5	0
Other service providers (/1)	0	0	1	0
Institutional actors (/10)	2	5	1	2
Promoters (/3)	0	1	0	2
Attractiveness creators (/3)	0	0	2	1
Total (/27)	4	9	9	5

Despite this, stakeholders do feel heard when initiatives are being developed: 11 out of 27 feel sufficiently heard, and 17 out of 27 at least partially (Table 11). This sense of being heard is particularly true at the local level with municipalities, where communication is seen as simpler and more accessible. However, there remains a real challenge at the national level: “if we are heard in our territory, there is sometimes a gap between local needs and central decision-making” (institutional actor).

Farmers also mentioned their difficulties in being understood with regard to bureaucratic burdens and legal constraints, which vary considerably from year to year. Half of the farmers interviewed (5 out of 10) felt sufficiently heard, which contrasts with their degree of satisfaction with initiatives. This discrepancy stems from the fact that, while they may be listened to and represented, they do not always feel truly heard. “I don’t feel that they really listen to us, and then they do what they want anyway,” explained one farmer. Yet few farmers try to actively respond to this lack of consideration and instead resign themselves to the situation. “We are not very satisfied with the infrastructure, but we don’t say anything either,” said one. The reason for this passivity lies in the individual barriers already mentioned, but also in the lack of initiative from institutions to engage with these farmers, which makes it even harder for them to mobilize resources to make their voices heard. “You have to be proactive, say what you think, it’s a huge pressure,” said a young farmer.

Table 11 – Stakeholders' perceived sense of being heard in rural development initiatives, by category (author, 2025)

	Sufficiently heard	Partially heard	Not sufficiently heard	No opinion
Farmers (/10)	5	1	3	1
Other service providers(/1)	1	0	0	0
Institutional actors (/10)	3	3	2	2
Promoters (/3)	0	1	0	2
Attractiveness creators (/3)	2	0	1	0
Total (/27)	11	5	6	5

III.2.b. Institutional actors must reaffirm their role and facilitate mutual knowledge and communication among all key actors in the agritourism system

Institutions play a central role in coordinating the tourism system, actively cooperating with all other categories of actors as well as with each other (see Table 5, p. 25). “The municipality is very open to cooperation,” said one institutional actor. They also possess the greatest level of mutual knowledge among actor categories, citing on average 5.9 actors important for the development of agritourism (see Table 4, p. 24). They are considered the most important category for agritourism development, cited by 19 out of 27 respondents. Consequently, institutions must be more active and proactive in order to structure the bioregional agritourism system.

This shift in scale is particularly important for facilitating the development of short supply chains, defined as the transition from local, marginal initiatives to a broader phenomenon integrated into the economy and public policies (Chiffolleau, 2017). In the current context, institutions are expected to take three directions:

- They must proactively engage with farmers, demonstrate understanding of their situation, and bring them together to facilitate networking around agritourism themes;
- They must coordinate among themselves to formalize agritourism development opportunities (financial support, training offers, mentoring programs, cooperation initiatives, promotional opportunities) in a way that is structured, clear, easily accessible, and tailored to the specificities of agritourism;
- They must more strongly advocate their claims to governmental bodies to ensure better recognition, particularly for securing the funding necessary for rural infrastructure development.

These expectations are particularly strong regarding municipalities (cited by 15 out of 27 respondents), the most frequently mentioned actors in the interview. Expectations were also directed towards other governmental bodies, notably LLKC and the ministries (Agriculture

and Economy), both cited by 6 out of 27 respondents. Other institutional actors, however, remain underrepresented despite the important role they play, such as LAGs, the Nature Conservation Agency, and the Vidzeme planning region, each cited by only 2 out of 27 respondents. Surprisingly, only 1 out of 27 respondents mentioned the bioregion. At present, it lacks the tools to implement concrete actions due to its horizontal and non-administrative management model. Nevertheless, even if institutions succeed in meeting these three directions, agritourism development will never take off without initiative from farmers.

III.2.c. Development must emerge from farmers' initiatives, which need to be facilitated and supported

The human and psychological barriers faced by farmers translate into doubts or concerns when the idea of creating an agritourism sector is raised: lack of workforce (cited by 4 out of 10 farmers), the time-consuming nature of the activity (4 out of 10, "time is something we don't have"), investment costs (3 out of 10), bureaucracy (2 out of 10), or even tourist behavior (1 out of 10, "there are dark sides to it"). If the initiative must come from farmers, it is unlikely to emerge unless it is facilitated and supported with appropriate tools. "I would be willing to collaborate, but I will probably not be the initiator of such collaboration," said one farmer.

However, it seems unlikely that public institutions will be able to provide this facilitation and support; several institutional actors mentioned constraints related to a lack of resources (time, money, qualified staff).

In many interviews, the idea emerged of having a body operating at the bioregional scale to assume this role. The possibility of a public bioregional institution does not seem to be under consideration, as stakeholders wish to maintain the freedom offered by the bioregion's informal status. Agricultural associations exist and could work on these issues, but none are specialized in agritourism nor operate at the bioregional scale. A more suitable proposal would be the creation of a private enterprise operating as a public-interest association. Private management would allow profitability-oriented governance, reducing dependence on public funding, while also offering greater legal autonomy than a public institution.

Its management model could be inspired by wind energy projects developed in Latvia: to encourage residents to support these projects, they are offered shares in the company, giving them decision-making power over how it is managed. Such a company could distribute shares among bioregion stakeholders, particularly farmers, to ensure local representation in decision-making. Its creation could serve as an economic argument to encourage new actors to join around bioregional values, whose objectives would be reflected in the company's expected outcomes. Initially, it could focus on agritourism, before diversifying to address other missions within the bioregion (food systems, waste management, etc.). This proposal remains a line of reflection, and even without necessarily creating such a body, there remains a need for discussion on its feasibility.

Nonetheless, while several options exist for defining governance of this system, it is equally important to ensure its long-term sustainability.

III.3. The need to integrate the agritourism system into a sustainable territorial tourism system

A recurring observation is the difficulty of sustaining initiatives over time, a challenge further exacerbated in the case of agritourism by the territorial inequalities faced by remote rural areas. There is therefore a genuine need to integrate this agritourism system into a sustainable territorial tourism system, in a context of local revitalization, growing attractiveness of rural areas, and specific expectations of agritourists. Indeed, the concepts of sustainable development and agritourism are closely linked (Foris et al., 2020). Similarly, the overall performance of short food supply chains is tied to the achievement of sustainability objectives (Corade et al., 2022). This agritourism system must therefore pay particular attention in its development to sustainability challenges at the bioregional level, whether economic, social, or environmental.

III.3.a. Sustainable preservation of the environment and natural heritage as a key challenge for maintaining territorial attractiveness

Nature is a central element of territorial identity and a major driver of tourism. “We do not realize how lucky we are,” said a farmer. Its preservation is therefore a key challenge in maintaining attractiveness: “it is our duty to protect it” (institutional actor). Yet, the polarization of tourism dynamics in limited areas exerts considerable pressure on them. “Tourism brings waste, noise, pollution in some places...” (institutional actor); “sometimes, there are too many tourists in certain places. We have to say: please, fewer tourists” (promoter). Because of this, tourism, despite its importance in the local economy, is often questioned and criticized: “we do not want people to damage nature, we want balance” (promoter). In response to this pressure, agritourism could serve as a tool to deconcentrate tourist flows by enabling a more balanced distribution of visitors across the territory, thus addressing the polarization of tourism dynamics.

At the same time, care must be taken to ensure that agritourism itself and its activities do not exert excessive pressure on the environment. In particular, the issue of infrastructure must be considered. While more on-farm infrastructure is needed to accommodate agritourists and organize activities, the expansion of such facilities could also impact the environment and landscape. “Not all places should be filled with tourist attractions; some should remain untouched” (institutional actor). Although construction restrictions exist (SIA “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment,” 2023), they do not apply outside the national park. However, the park’s boundaries are not fixed: five additional zones are currently being studied for inclusion (see [Figure 4](#), p. 10), and landscapes do not stop at administrative borders. Still, this polarization affects not only tourism dynamics but also social and economic ones.

III.3.b. Recognizing territorial specificities for the sustainable integration of remote rural areas into bioregional dynamics

Agritourism may also be seen as an opportunity to integrate remote rural areas and their residents into the economic and social dynamics of the bioregion, helping to address the challenges they face (depopulation, declining attractiveness, lack of services...). Ensuring

such sustainable integration through agritourism must be a central concern. The bioregion should not become yet another tool of exclusion and marginalization for these areas and their communities. For this to happen, agritourism development must offer equal opportunities to all actors in the bioregion, regardless of their geographical location; it must not be concentrated only around the cities of municipalities. Development should also pay greater attention to territorial specificities, particularly ultra-local challenges.

To guarantee this integration of rural territories and better account for their situations, it is essential to address the lack of statistical data on agritourism. Data are needed on what works best in these areas, ideally including tools to analyze the performance of agritourism ventures, in order to guide, support, and reassure farmers interested in this type of activity. Among the farmers interviewed, 8/10 did not consider this lack problematic, since production remains their main entrepreneurial goal. However, the other two disagreed: “it would be useful to us; we probably don’t know much about it for now” said one, “we would need something easy to read” said the other. Nevertheless, 9/10 believe that more statistical data could encourage farmers to develop agritourism on their farms, since it is perceived as a reliable source of supplementary income and one less dependent on the uncertainties of agricultural production. According to them, such data could also help attract tourists more easily and stimulate the activity of farmers already engaged in it. Finally, these data could serve as the basis for developing a model pathway for creating agritourism ventures tailored to territorial specificities. Farmers’ demand for statistical data also reflects a broader issue: the needs of residents in these territories.

III.3.c. The necessary consideration of local inhabitants for the sustainable development of agritourism initiatives

Residents and local communities are not sufficiently taken into account in the discussion on agritourism. Only 5/27 of the actors interviewed mentioned them, even though, while peripheral to the agritourism system, they are directly exposed to the positive or negative externalities generated by it.

Rural residents value their tranquility: “the bigger the fence between you and your neighbor, the better you live” (institutional actor). It is therefore necessary to assess their openness to agritourism development before implementing any strategy, especially since tensions related to rural tourism already exist. An institutional actor reported a resident saying: “they come into my garden and take photos of me as if I were a monkey in a zoo.”

Another important aspect for these populations is the exposure to neo-rural migrations driven by agritourism (Lambert, 1991). This phenomenon can bring certain benefits to vulnerable territories (Lambert, 1991; Tomay & Ragadics, 2025): population renewal, rehabilitation of housing and services, growth of the local service economy... But it also poses risks of rural gentrification that may reinforce socio-economic inequalities among local residents (Tommasi, 2018; Moragues-Faus, 2025): rising land and housing prices, scarcity of affordable housing, marginalization of working-class populations, development of social enclaves, power imbalances, food insecurity... Beyond inequalities, these migrations may generate conflicts around local values, between populations wishing to preserve traditional values and newcomers bringing different ones (Tommasi, 2018; Tomay & Ragadics, 2025;

Zhang, 2025). These migrations result in a gradual transformation of local values and, more generally, of the rural landscape (Tommasi, 2018; Moragues-Faus, 2025; Zhang, 2025). The urban sprawl of Sigulda into surrounding rural areas is the first symptom of such gentrification, and complaints have already been voiced about this peri-urbanization encroaching on the typical agricultural landscape of the bioregion.

However, considering the local resident does not only mean those in rural areas, but also those in urban centers. The range of policies on short supply chains and food systems (Aļeksējeva, 2024; Vidzemes plānošanas reģions, 2024) prompts reflection on the role of local agritourism as a driver of food relocalization and circular economy development. While urban residents enjoy greater purchasing power, the local tourist has not been mentioned in the interviews (only domestic or international ones were). Yet, agritourism plays an educational and awareness-raising role, thanks to the direct producer-consumer link and the emotions conveyed during the experience (Dubois & Schmitz, 2011; Dembovska & Silicka, 2014; Foris et al., 2020). With effective consideration of the local tourist in its development, through targeted promotion of on-farm sales and attractiveness creators (markets, festivals), agritourism could contribute to changing urban consumption habits and thus reinforce the territorial anchoring of the bioregional food system.

Conclusion

The Gauja bioregion was established around the Gauja national park, the largest and oldest national park in Latvia, which also stands as a major tourist destination in Vidzeme. It emerged through development projects centered on a typical form of local agriculture, consisting of small and medium-sized family farms largely oriented toward organic production and equipped with processing facilities, which provide numerous benefits for the preservation of the park's landscape and biodiversity. However, this typical agriculture is now facing several challenges: increasing land pressure, a lack of generational renewal, dependence on imported inputs, and market difficulties. As a result, it is in some areas being replaced by large-scale entrepreneurial farms or intensive forestry. This shift entails a loss of identity and cultural heritage, a reduction in territorial food autonomy, as well as a decline in landscape diversity, thereby undermining the region's attractiveness. To address these challenges, sustain this form of agriculture, and make it more dynamic, one proposed solution is to enhance the socio-economic valorization of local products through agritourism, with particular attention to the role of short supply chains in mitigating its market difficulties. Agritourism remains a relatively new field of study, and farmer participation in initiatives promoting it has so far been limited. Moreover, both agritourism and short supply chains are central to numerous multi-scalar and multi-actor policies. This research project therefore aimed to identify several strategies to foster the development of agritourism in the bioregion.

To this end, an exploratory study was conducted through hybrid interviews with actors of the bioregional agritourism system, structured around six themes identified in the literature: territorial identity, socio-economic context, state of knowledge, training needs, infrastructure, and inter-actor cooperation. The study involved 27 stakeholders (10 farmers, 1 other service provider, 10 institutional actors, 3 promoters, and 3 attractiveness creators). While the sample has certain limitations, it nevertheless remains broadly representative of the bioregional agritourism system and its specificities. The interviews helped identify a set of barriers (lack of structuring and coordination among actors, human and psychological barriers, territorial inequalities, insufficient infrastructure, limited accessibility of local products) as well as drivers (strong territorial identity, existing development opportunities, favorable contextual factors, clearly identified demand, and an emerging coherent supply) that manifest across several levels: at the scale of the agritourism system as a whole, within intra-bioregional dynamics, and at the product level itself. These identified barriers and drivers led to the proposal of three main strategies for the development of agritourism in the bioregion. These strategies revolve around an initial need to define the bioregional agritourism system (where, based on what, and with whom), the establishment of clear governance to structure this system and create a favorable framework for initiative development, and finally, a stronger integration of sustainability criteria to ensure its long-term viability.

At this stage, these results must be discussed, critiqued, and debated by all stakeholders currently involved or potentially involved in the bioregional agritourism system. This includes both those who were interviewed and those who could not be reached. Such exchanges are particularly important given that the results were obtained in relation to the specific research objectives of the study. It is therefore essential for local stakeholders to reflect on the

ultimate purpose of this development in order to align it more closely with their own objectives. To go further, two complementary studies could be undertaken:

✦ First, a quantitative study conducted as a survey among consumers themselves would refine the results already obtained (regarding their expectations, consumption habits, and perceptions of the topic) and provide agritourism system stakeholders with additional data to guide the proposed development strategies, thereby ensuring their relevance and feasibility.

✦ Second, a comparative study with other similar European initiatives, such as Italian urban bioregions or French regional natural parks, would offer further insights for the development of a bioregional agritourism destination. This would involve aspects such as governance, financing and cooperation models, as well as potential economic, social, and ecological impacts resulting from decision-making within these initiatives.

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Appendix 1 - Interview guide

Introduction

Hello, my name is Romain and I'm a French student in the final year of my agronomy studies. I specialize in territorial development, meaning I approach agriculture through the lenses of economics, social sciences, and politics.

I'm currently doing my final internship in Latvia, focusing on the preservation and galvanization of the bioregional agricultural landscape and its specific characteristics in the face of current challenges. To do so, I'm conducting research on identifying strategies for the development of agritourism in the bioregion, aiming to better promote local products economically and socially—particularly through the development of short supply chains.

This interview will last about 2 hours and aims to identify the barriers and opportunities for agritourism in the bioregion. It will cover six themes: identity, economic context, knowledge base, infrastructure, training needs, and cooperation.

This interview will be anonymized, meaning that anything you say will not be publicly attributed to you.

- 0. Do you have any questions about this interview before we begin?

Before we start :

- 1. Could you please introduce yourself?

follow-up questions : name? profession? background?

- 2. Could you briefly describe your organization?

follow-up questions :

2.1. For farmers: What do you produce? What is your farm size? How many people work on the farm? Do you have a processing facility? Are you involved in agritourism?

2.2. For other service providers: What products do you offer? Who are your customers? How many clients do you serve per day?

2.3. For suppliers: What actions do you carry out? Who is your target audience? How many people do you reach?

2.4. For institutions: What are your missions? Who do you support?

2.5. For attractivity creators: What's the story behind your organization? What events do you organize? How many people do you attract?

- 3. Can you tell me about your work environment?

follow-up questions : What is your relationship with the bioregion? Do you spend a lot of your time in the bioregion? Do you consider it to be a good work environment?

Theme 1: Identity

- 4. Do you feel a sense of belonging to the bioregion?

follow-up questions : If not, why? At what scale do you feel the strongest sense of belonging (local, regional, national)?

- 5. In your opinion, what defines the identity of your territory?

follow-up questions : Its location and natural features? Historical and cultural heritage (including intangible heritage and local traditions)? Agriculture?

- 6. What are the specific features of local products?

follow-up questions : What makes a product "local"? Do they have specific qualities? Do you think there is a visible diversity of local products in the region? Are they seasonally available?

- 7. Do you think your territory's identity and products are sufficiently promoted?

follow-up questions : Is there communication about the territory's identity? Are local products promoted commercially (restaurants, supermarkets, etc.)? Are consumers informed enough about the territory's identity? And about the quality and specificities of local products?

- **8.1 For farmers:** Would you like to offer more local products in your establishment?

follow-up question : If not, why? Is local valorization of your product important to you?

- **8.2 For other service providers (restaurants, shops...)** : Would you like to offer more local products in your establishment?

follow-up question : If not, why? Is the local valorization of products important to you? Would you be willing to highlight more the specificities of the local products you sell (producer name, production location, production conditions)?

Theme 2: Economic Context

- 9. Can you tell me a bit about the current economic and social situation in the bioregion?

follow-up questions : Is there unemployment increase? Are shops closing? Is there rural depopulation? Is the area losing attractiveness?

- 10. What role does agriculture play in the local economy?

follow-up questions : Jobs (if possible : how many)? Wealth creation? What types of agriculture are practiced (family-based, extensive, organic, local, for export)? Production volumes?

- **11. For farmers:** What are the main constraints you face (financial, personal, regulatory...)?

- 12. Is there financial support for diversifying farm activities?

follow-up questions : Who provides this support? Do they fund projects related to rural tourism?

- 13. What role does tourism play in the local economy?

follow-up questions : Jobs (if possible : how many)? Wealth creation?

Theme 3: Knowledge Base

- 14. Could you give me your own definition of agritourism?

follow-up question : Do you feel you have a good understanding of the concept?

Definition of agritourism: Agritourism generally refers to staying on a farm while discovering the local culture and traditions. It can also include local cultural festivals, museums, handicraft exhibitions, cultural events, and attractions. Agritourism can take different forms:

- ❖ Accommodation (farm stays, bed and breakfasts on farms, farm camping...)
- ❖ Activities (hosting school groups, farm golf, banquet halls, farm restaurants, butcher shops...)

- 15. Generally speaking, do you think certain areas of the territory attract more tourists?

follow-up question : Here is a map of the area surrounding the national park. Could you circle in green the areas that you believe are the most attractive to tourists?

Gaujas nacionālā parka un tā tuvākās apkārtnes galveno ģeogrāfisko elementu shēma
(Glatthoud, 2025, no Open Street Maps, 2025)

- 16. Do you have an idea of the typical profile of tourists participating in agritourism activities?

follow-up questions : Age group? Social class? Where do they come from?

- 17. In your view, what might attract tourists within this type of tourism?

- 18. Do you sense a demand from tourists for local products?

follow-up question : What are their expectations regarding these products : quality? price? origin?

- 19. Today, is it easy to find information about agritourism in the bioregion?

follow-up questions : Who do people turn to for information? Is the information complete enough?

- **20. For farmers** : Do you find the lack of data on agritourism to be a problem?

follow-up questions : Do you think having more data would increase farmers' confidence and encourage them to engage in tourism activities?

Theme 4: Training Needs

- 21.1. Do farmers currently have the human and commercial skills needed to organize agritourism activities?

- **21.2. For farmers**: Do you feel you have the necessary human and commercial skills for organizing agritourism activities?

follow-up questions : How many languages do they / you speak? Are they / you comfortable with customer relations?

- 22. Are there training programs for agritourism to develop these skills?

- 23. Is there accompaniment / mentoring available for such projects (professional, legal, financial)?

Theme 5: Infrastructures

- 24. Do you think it's easy enough to reach farms?

follow-up questions : Are the road infrastructures good? Can one get there without a car? Are farms well connected to the road network?

- 25. Do you think the region is sufficiently equipped with tourist infrastructure (restaurants, hotels, amusement parks, toilets, etc.)?

follow-up question : If not, why?

- 26. Are these infrastructures evenly distributed across the territory?

follow-up question : On the previous map, could you circle in red the areas where you think there is a lack of tourism infrastructure?

- **27. For farmers:** Does your farm have the necessary infrastructure to host tourists?

follow-up questions : For accommodation? For organizing indoor/outdoor recreational activities? For selling products?

- **28.1. For farmers:** Is it easy for you to supply local businesses with your products?

follow-up questions : Regarding delivery time? Transportation cost?

- **28.2. For other service providers:** Is it easy for you to source local products?

follow-up questions : Regarding delivery time? Transportation cost? Are there uncertainties about product volumes?

Theme 6: Cooperation

- 29. Who do you consider the most important stakeholders in the agritourism system?

follow-up question : What is their role?

- 30. Do you collaborate with other stakeholders within the tourism system?

follow-up questions : With whom? How does the collaboration work? Are there conflicting visions? If so, what causes them?

- 31. Would you be willing to collaborate more with other tourism system stakeholders around agritourism?

follow-up question : If not, why?

- **32. For farmers:** In the context of building an agritourism sector, what doubts or constraints would you have?

follow-up question : Is autonomy an important concept for you?

- 33. Are there any initiatives to facilitate cooperation between stakeholders on agritourism?

follow-up questions : Who initiated them? Are they effective? If there are no initiatives or they are ineffective, why?

- 34. Are you satisfied with how rural development initiatives are currently managed?

follow-up questions : Do you feel listened to and included in these initiatives? Are there governance issues?

Conclusion

Thank you for your answers:

- 35. On a more personal note, has this interview raised any new questions for you, or ideas you'd like to explore further?
- 36. Is there anything you'd like to add before we finish?
- 37. Would you be interested in receiving the final report once I've written it?

Let me remind you that this interview will remain anonymous, and thank you again for your time. I remain available via email for any further discussion or clarification.

Appendix 2 – Technical sheet of the translation system

System description:

While the interviewee is speaking, a cardioid microphone is placed next to them. This unidirectional capture system reduces the recording of speech from the interviewer and the interpreter. The microphone is connected via USB to a laptop running the Bluestacks program. Bluestacks is an emulator capable of reading APK files (the standard Android format). It allows the execution of the Google Translate APK, which, unlike the PC version of the application, features a transcription mode. This mode enables uninterrupted, real-time translation of the interviewee's speech from Latvian into French. Furthermore, thanks to Google's service connectivity, the entire transcription can be automatically saved to Google Drive at the end of the interview.

Limitations of this system include:

- ✘ Google Translate had difficulty recognizing certain accents;
- ✘ When the speech flow was too long (several minutes without pause), Google Translate sometimes struggled to process the incoming data;
- ✘ When the distance between the interviewee and the interpreter was too small, the cardioid microphone was not always effective enough to isolate the interviewee's speech; in such cases, Google Translate attempted to generate sentences simultaneously from both speakers' utterances.

Appendix 3 – Image gallery of the natural and cultural heritage elements of the bioregion

Gauja River

Geological features

Gutmanis Cave (Sigulda municipality)

Outcrops revealing the geological structure of the subsoil (Sigulda municipality)

Fauna and flora

Lupins and mallards

Storks and bitter bolete mushrooms

Turaida Castle (Sigulda municipality)

Views from the top of the tower over the Gauja River and from the courtyard

Footprints of chickens and sheep dating back to the Middle Ages

Statue

City of Sigulda

Handmade, traditionally crafted clothing

Sigulda municipality brand logo "S!" and nature center

Old and new Sigulda castles

Lutheran church

Village of Taurupe (Ogre municipality)

Former Soviet agro-village in decline, once inhabited by kolkhoz workers during the era of forced collectivization

Postal station museum

Village of Priekuļi (Cēsis municipality)

Clover field in crop rotation at the AREI varietal experimentation laboratory

Priekuļi cemetery

City of Cēsis

Medieval Cēsis Castle and the lower promenade pond, around which the annual LAMPA festival is organized

Orthodox church

Local SlowFood Market, Straupe village (Cēsis municipality)

Village of Līgatne (Cēsis municipality)

Tasting of local wines made from various fruits and berries cultivated or foraged near the village

Troglodyte caves originally used for fermentation

Typical red-brick buildings of Līgatne, repurposed after the Soviet period

Farms

Livestock: dairy cows, lambs and sheep, chickens

Organic blueberry field

Local products: aged cheeses, canned lamb meat, honey, herbal teas

Historical photographs shown by farmers

Photographs of manor interiors: these buildings once symbolized the power of landowners during the era of serfdom

Photograph of the interior of a klub, a former meeting and festivity hall for rural inhabitants during the Soviet era, later converted into a sheepfold